

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

№ 11

2025

ISSN: 2992-8982

<https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz/>

IQTISODIYOT&TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Bosh muharrir:

Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich

Elektron nashr. 2025-yil, noyabr.

Bosh muharrir o'rinbosari:

Karimov Norboy G'aniyevich

Muharrir:

Qurbonov Sherzod Ismatillayevich

Tahrir hay'ati:

Salimov Oqil Umrzoqovich, O'zbekiston Fanlar akademiyasi akademigi
Abduraxmanov Kalandar Xodjayevich, O'zbekiston Fanlar akademiyasi akademigi
Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Rae Kvon Chung, Janubiy Koreya, TDIU faxriy professori, "Nobel" mukofoti laureati
Osman Mesten, Turkiya parlamenti a'zosi, Turkiya – O'zbekiston do'stlik jamiyati rahbari
Axmedov Durbek Kudratillayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Axmedov Sayfullo Normatovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Abduraxmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Kalonov Muxiddin Baxritdinovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Siddiqova Sadoqat G'afforovna, pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Xudoyqulov Sadirdin Karimovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Maxmudov Nosir, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Yuldashev Mutallib Ibragimovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Samadov Asqarjon Nishonovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, professor
Slizovskiy Dimitriy Yegorovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Mustafakulov Sherzod Igamberdiyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Axmedov Ikrom Akramovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Eshtayev Alisher Abdug'aniyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Xajiyev Baxtiyor Dushaboyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Hakimov Nazar Hakimovich, falsafa fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Musayeva Shoira Azimovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), professor
Ali Konak (Ali Ko'nak), iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor (Turkiya)
Cham Tat Huei, falsafa fanlari doktori (PhD), professor (Malayziya)
Foziljonov Ibrohimjon Sotvoldixo'ja o'g'li, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dots.
Utayev Uktam Choriyevich, O'z.Respub. Bosh prokuraturasi boshqarma boshlig'i o'rinbosari
Ochilov Farkhod, O'zbekiston Respublikasi Bosh prokuraturasi IJQKD boshlig'i
Buzrukxonov Sarvarxon Munavvarxonovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Axmedov Javohir Jamolovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Toxirov Jaloliddin Ochil o'g'li, texnika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), katta o'qituvchi
Bobobekov Ergash Abdumalikovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), v.b. dots.
Djudi Smetana, pedagogika fanlari nomzodi, dotsent (AQSH)
Krissi Lyuis, pedagogika fanlari nomzodi, dotsent (AQSH)
Glazova Marina Viktorovna, Iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (Moskva)
Nosirova Nargiza Jamoliddin qizi, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Sevil Piriyeva Karaman, falsafa fanlari doktori (PhD) (Turkiya)
Mirzaliyev Sanjar Makhamatjon o'g'li, TDIU ITI departamenti rahbari
Ochilov Bobur Baxtiyor o'g'li, TDIU katta o'qituvchisi
Golisheva Yelena Vyacheslavovna, Iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent.

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Editorial board:

Salimov Okil Umrzokovich, Academician of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan

Abdurakhmanov Kalandar Khodjavevich, Academician of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan

Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor

Rae Kwon Chung, South Korea, Honorary Professor at TSUE, Nobel Prize Laureate

Osman Mesten, Member of the Turkish Parliament, Head of the Turkey–Uzbekistan Friendship Society

Akhmedov Durbek Kudratillayevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Akhmedov Sayfullo Normatovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Abdurakhmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Kalonov Mukhiddin Bakhriddinovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Siddikova Sadokat Gafforovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Pedagogical Sciences

Khudoykulov Sadirdin Karimovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Makhmudov Nosir, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Yuldashev Mutallib Ibragimovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Samadov Askarjon Nishonovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Professor

Slizovskiy Dmitriy Yegorovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor

Mustafakulov Sherzod Igamberdiyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Akhmedov Ikrom Akramovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Eshtayev Alisher Abduganiyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Khajiyev Bakhtiyor Dushaboyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Khakimov Nazar Khakimovich, Doctor of Philosophy (DSc), Professor

Musayeva Shoira Azimovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Professor

Ali Konak, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor (Turkey)

Cham Tat Huei, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD), Professor (Malaysia)

Foziljonov Ibrokhimjon Sotvoldikhoja ugli, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Associate Professor

Utayev Uktam Choriyevich, Deputy Head of Department, Prosecutor General's Office of Uzbekistan

Ochilov Farkhod, Head of DCEC, Prosecutor General's Office of Uzbekistan

Buzrukkhonov Sarvarkhon Munavvarkhonovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor

Akhmedov Javokhir Jamolovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences

Tokhirov Jaloliddin Ochil ugli, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Technical Sciences, Senior Lecturer

Bobobekov Ergash Abdumalikovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Acting Associate Professor

Judi Smetana, Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor (USA)

Chrissy Lewis, Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor (USA)

Glazova Marina Victorovna, Doctor of Sciences in Economics (Moscow))

Nosirova Nargiza Jamoliddin kizi, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Associate Professor

Sevil Piriyeva Karaman, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) (Turkey)

Mirzaliyev Sanjar Makhmatjon ugli, Head of the Department of Scientific Research and Innovations, TSUE

Ochilov Bobur Bakhtiyor ugli, Senior lecturer at TSUI

Golisheva Yelena Vyacheslavovna, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor.

Ekspertlar kengashi:

Berkinov Bazarbay, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Po'latov Baxtiyor Alimovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Aliyev Bekdavlat Aliyevich, falsafa fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Isakov Janabay Yakubbayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Xalikov Suyun Ravshanovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Rustamov Ilhomiddin, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Hakimov Ziyodulla Ahmadovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, dotsent
Kamilova Iroda Xusniddinovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
G'afurov Doniyor Orifovich, pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Fayziyev Oybek Raximovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Tuxtabayev Jamshid Sharafetdinovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Xamidova Faridaxon Abdulkarim qizi, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, dotsent
Yaxshiboyeva Laylo Abdisattorovna, katta o'qituvchi
Babayeva Zuhra Yuldashevna, mustaqil tadqiqotchi
Komilova Nilufar Karshiboyevna, Geografiya fanlari doktori, professori
Umirzoqov Ja'sur Artiqboy o'g'li, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), dotsent
Zebo Kuldasheva, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), dotsent

Board of Experts:

Berkinov Bazarbay, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Pulatov Bakhtiyor Alimovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor
Aliyev Bekdavlat Aliyevich, Doctor of Philosophy (DSc), Professor
Isakov Janabay Yakubbayevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Khalikov Suyun Ravshanovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Rustamov Ilhomiddin, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Khakimov Ziyodulla Akhmadovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Kamilova Iroda Xusniddinovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics
Gafurov Doniyor Orifovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Pedagogy
Fayziyev Oybek Raximovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics, Associate Professor
Tukhtabayev Jamshid Sharafetdinovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics, Associate Professor
Khamidova Faridaxon Abdulkarimovna, Doctor of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Yakhshiboyeva Laylo Abdisattorovna, Senior Lecturer
Babayeva Zuhra Yuldashevna, Independent Researcher
Komilova Nilufar Karshiboyevna, Doctor of Geographical Sciences, Professor
Umirzokov Jasur Artiqboy ugli, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Associate Professor
Zebo Kuldasheva, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Associate Professor

- 08.00.01 Iqtisodiyot nazariyasi
- 08.00.02 Makroiqtisodiyot
- 08.00.03 Sanoat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.04 Qishloq xo'jaligi iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.05 Xizmat ko'rsatish tarmoqlari iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.06 Ekonometrika va statistika
- 08.00.07 Moliya, pul muomalasi va kredit
- 08.00.08 Buxgalteriya hisobi, iqtisodiy tahlil va audit
- 08.00.09 Jahon iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.10 Demografiya. Mehnat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.11 Marketing
- 08.00.12 Mintaqaviy iqtisodiyot
- 08.00.13 Menejment
- 08.00.14 Iqtisodiyotda axborot tizimlari va texnologiyalari
- 08.00.15 Tadbirkorlik va kichik biznes iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.16 Raqamli iqtisodiyot va xalqaro raqamli integratsiya
- 08.00.17 Turizm va mehmonxona faoliyati

Muassis: "Ma'rifat-print-media" MChJ

Hamkorlarimiz: Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti, O'zR Tabiat resurslari vazirligi, O'zR Bosh prokuraturasi huzuridagi IJQK departamenti.

Jurnalning ilmiyligi:

“Yashil” iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot” jurnali

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy ta'lim, fan va innovatsiyalar vazirligi huzuridagi Oliy attestatsiya komissiyasi rayosatining 2023-yil 1-apreldagi 336/3-sonli qarori bilan ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

MUNDARIJA

YASHIL TRANSPORT SIYOSATINING BARQAROR RIVOJLANISH VA TARMOQLARARO INTEGRATSIYADAGI O'RNINI.....	21
Rahmonov Rasul Ne'matovich	
BANK AKTIVLARI VA PASSIVLARINI BOSHQARISHNI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	34
Safarov Sanjar Ravshan o'g'li	
O'ZBEKISTONNING INVESTITSION JOZIBADORLIGINI OSHIRISH STRATEGIYALARI.....	38
Madraximova Irodaxon Sherzodbek qizi	
HUDDUDIY XIZMAT KO'RSATISH KORXONALARIDA MENEJMENT SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISHNING RAQAMLI TRANSFORMATSIYA MODELINI	43
Maxmudova Nozimaxon Baxriddinxonovna	
DAVLAT-XUSUSIY SHERIKLIGINING MEXANIZMINI SAMARALI TASHKILLASHTIRISHDA MOLIYAVIY MANBALARNI SHAKLLANTIRISHNI YO'NALISHLARI	56
Mansurov Mansur Alisherovich	
ANTIKRIZISLI BOSHQARUV TIZIMLARIDA RANGLI SIGNAL MEXANIZMLARINING FUNKSIYALARI.....	61
Aliqulov Aziz Haydarjonovich	
XODIMLARNI MOTIVATSIYALASHNING XALQARO MODELLARINI O'ZBEKISTON KORXONALARIDA QO'LLASH IMKONIYATLARI.....	66
Yormamatov Qodirjon Juraqulovich	
RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT OMILLARI VA ULARNING QISHLOQ XO'JALIGI KORXONALARINING SAMARADORLIGIGA TA'SIRI	71
Yaxshiyev Shahzod Sherali o'g'li	
OLIY TA'LIM MUASSASALARI VA MEHNAT BOZORI INTEGRATSIYASI BO'YICHA XORIY TAJRIBALARI	78
Haqqulov Fazliddin Faxriddinovich	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOTGA O'TISHDA RIVOJLANGAN VA RIVOJLANAYOTGAN DAVLATLAR TAJRIBASI.....	84
Aripov Abdulaziz Sakijonovich	
YASHIL ENERGETIKA RIVOJLANISHINING IQTISODIY SAMARADORLIGINI EKONOMETRIK BAHOLASH.....	89
Bobokulova Muhabbat Mahammadiyeva	
ELEKTRON TO'LOVLAR VA POS TIZIMLARI — KICHIK BIZNESDA SAMARASI VA XAVFLARI	93
To'liqinov Dilshodxo'ja Olim o'g'li	
MINTAQADA RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOTNI BARQAROR RIVOJLANTIRISHNING ISTIQBOLLI YO'NALISHLARI	98
Yusubov In'omjon Ikram o'g'li	
SOLIQ SIYOSATINI RAQAMLI BOSHQARISH ORQALI BUDJET DAROMADLARINI BARQARORLASHTIRISH STRATEGIYASI.....	103
Xodjimatov Xamidullo Mamirjonovich	
OZIQ-OVQAT TOVARLARI B2B BOZORINI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA ZAMONAVIY MARKETING STRATEGIYALARIDAN FOYDALANISH	108
Hayitboyeva Ullijon Bobonazar qizi	
FARMASEVTIKA SANOATIDA INVESTITSION FAOLIYAT SAMARADORLIGINI BAHOLASH	113
Yaqubov Timurbek G'anibekovich	
SHAXSNI OVOZI ASOSIDA IDENTIFIKATSIYALASH VA AUTENTIFIKATSIYALASH ALGORITMLARI	123
Ozoda Sabirova Shermamaxamatovna	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOT — BARQAROR RIVOJLANISH GENERATORI.....	129
Berdibekova Dilfuza Xoldorbekovna	
CHET EL MEHMONXONA TARMOQLARINING BRENDING STRATEGIYALARINI O'RGANISH.....	133
Ergashev Oybek Mamarasul o'g'li	

MILLIY IQTISODIYOTDA KICHIK BIZNES VA XUSUSIY TADBIRKORLIK SOHASINING MOLIYAVIY SAMARADORLIGINI BAHOLASHNING USLUBIY JIHLATLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	144
Arzikulov Otabek Ali o'g'li	
TRANSPORT TIZIMI SOHASI KORXONALARINING INNOVATSION SALOHİYATINI BAHOLASH YO'NALISHLARI	152
Ismailov Akmal Maxsudovich, Abilqosimova Shaxlo Sodiq qizi	
MEHMONXONALAR SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISHDA XODIMLARNING O'RNI VA AHAMIYATI	158
Abdusamidov Sarvar Adxamovich, Normurodov Tal'at Normurod o'g'li	
KORXONALARDA HR TIZIMINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH YO'NALISHLARI	163
Aminova Shaxnoza Aziz qizi	
JAHON IQTISODIYOTIDA OZIQ-OVQAT XAFSIZLIK RO'LI.....	168
Abdusamatov Barkamol Rustamjon o'g'li	
ТУРИСТИЧЕСКИЕ РЕСУРСЫ КАРАКАЛПАКСТАНА И СУЩЕСТВУЮЩАЯ ИНФРАСТРУКТУРА	174
Хошимова Камилла Навфал қизи	
DAVLAT-XUSUSIY SHERIKLIK MEKANIZMLARI: REKREATIONS TURIZM SOHASIDA QO'LLASH TAJRIBASI VA ISTIQBOLLARI.....	184
Najmitdinov G'ayratbek Sharifovich	
O'ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASIDA VIRTUAL TA'LIM PLATFORMALARI: TEXNIK VA PEDAGOGIK TALABLAR, TIZIMLI TAHLIL VA IQTISODIY JIHLATLAR	189
Turayeva Adiba Ikramovna	
ICHKI AUDIT TIZIMI VA UNI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH MASALALARI	193
Nuridinova Barchinoy Xusniddin qizi	
MINTAQA IQTISODIYOTIDA SUV RESURSLARIDAN FOYDALANISHNING IQTISODIY SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH YO'LLARI	199
Xaitbaev Jasurbek Otaxanovich	
MINTAQANING EKSPORT SALOHİYATINI OSHIRISHNING TASHKILIY-IQTISODIY MEKANIZMI.....	204
Raimboyeva Mashhura Davronbek qizi	
SURXONDARYO VILOYATIDA RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA XODIMLARNI BOSHQARISH TIZIMINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	210
Jobborov Anvar Egamberdiyevich	
ISLOMIY MOLIYALASHTIRISHDA RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALAR VA SUN'IY INTELLEKTNING DOLZARBLIGI	217
Nazarov Nodirjon Namoz o'g'li	
JISMONIY SHAXSLARNING MOL-MULKINI SOLIQQA TORTISH MASALALARI	222
Mamadjanov Shuxrat Jalolidinovich	
ENTREPRENEURSHIP AND BUSINESS MANAGEMENT IN UZBEKISTAN	225
Abdukhalikova Komila Abdukhalikovna	
BANKLARDA BARQARORLIKNI TA'MINLASH UCHUN RAQAMLI YECHIMLARNI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	229
Saydamatova Muxlisabonu Rasuljon qizi	
PAXTA-TO'QIMACHILIK SANOATINI MODERNIZATSIYA QILISH YO'NALISHLARI: TAHLIL VA TAKLIFLAR	233
Abdullayev Hamidulla Abdug'ani o'g'li	
WAYS TO IMPROVE THE EFFICIENCY OF STATE FINANCIAL REGULATION MECHANISMS IN ENSURING THE CAPITALIZATION OF INSURANCE ORGANIZATIONS	238
Abdullaev Erkinjon Azamovich	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOTNI SHAKLLANTIRISHDA YASHIL MOLIYALASHTIRISHNING NAZARIY JIHLATLARI	245
Xalikov S. X.	
QISHLOQ XO'JALIGI MAHSULOTLARI BOZORIDA KORXONALAR RAQOBATBARDOSHLIGINI OSHIRISHDA MARKETING STRATEGIYALARIDAN FOYDALANISH	245
Xudayberganov Jasur Baxodirovich	
WAYS TO IMPROVE THE EFFICIENCY OF STATE FINANCIAL REGULATION MECHANISMS IN ENSURING THE CAPITALIZATION OF INSURANCE ORGANIZATIONS	251
Abdullaev Erkinjon Azamovich	

NATIJAVIYLIKKA YO'NALTIRILGAN BUDJETLASHTIRISH JARAYONINING NAZARIY-USLUBIY ASOSLARI VA UNING O'ZIGA XOS XUSUSIYATLARI.....	257
Allakuliyev Akmal Baltayevich	
SURXONDARYO VILOYATIDA RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA XODIMLARNI BOSHQARISH TIZIMINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	261
Jobborov Anvar Egamberdiyevich	
TO'QIMACHILIK KORXONALARIDA BOSHQARUV TIZIMINI RESURLARNI OPTIMALLASHTIRISH ORQALI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	268
Avulchayeva Feruza Jurakuziyevna	
BANKLARDA BARQARORLIKNI TA'MINLASH UCHUN RAQAMLI YECHIMLARNI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	272
Saydamatova Muxlisabonu Rasuljon qizi	
ZAMONAVIY ISH JOYLARINI SHAKLLANTIRISHDA AYOLLARNING ROLI	276
Tulyaganova Aziza	
ISLOMIY MOLIYALASHTIRISHDA RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALAR VA SUN'IY INTELEKTNING DOLZARBLIGI.....	281
Nazarov Nodirjon Namoz o'g'li	
TURIZM MARKETINGINING NAZARIY ASOSLARI, ZAMONAVIY YO'NALISHLARI VA UNI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH ISTIQBOLLARI.....	286
Xamidov Otabek Bakidjanovich	
KICHIK BIZNES VA XUSUSIY TADBIRKORLIK SOHASINING IQTISODIY KO'RSATKICHLAR TIZIMINI STATISTIK BAHOLASHNING USLUBIY JIHATLARI	290
Arzikulov Otabek Ali o'g'li	
ЭКОЛОГАМ ПОЧЕТ И УВАЖЕНИЕ	298
Максудова Шахиста	
DEBITOR VA KREDITOR QARZDORLIKNING MOHIYATI VA ULARNING O'ZGARISH TENDENSIYALARI	304
Jo'raev Farruxbek Muxiddin o'g'li	
O'ZBEKISTONDA ISLOMIY MOLIYALASHTIRISH XIZMATLARI BOZORINI RIVOJLANTIRISH ISTIQBOLLARI.....	307
Inomjonov Islomjon Iloxomjon o'g'li	
ENTREPRENEURSHIP AND BUSINESS MANAGEMENT IN UZBEKISTAN	311
Abdukhaliqova Komila Abdukhaliqovna	
МОБИЛЬНЫЕ ТЕХНОЛОГИИ КАК СРЕДСТВО ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ ИССЛЕДОВАТЕЛЬСКИХ КОМПЕТЕНЦИЙ БУДУЩИХ ИНЖЕНЕРОВ.....	315
Хурамова Фарангиз Учкун кизи	
ЦИФРОВИЗАЦИЯ НАЛОГОВ И АКЦИЗНАЯ РЕФОРМА УЗБЕКИСТАНА В ВТО	319
Дамир Рустамович Абдулов	
BANK TIZIMIDAGI ISLOHOTLAR SHAROITIDA LIKVIDLILIK RISKINI BOSHQARISHNI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH YO'LLARI.....	324
Alimov Baxtiyor Murodovich	
BANK AUDITINING NAZARIY-USLUBIY ASOSLARI VA UNI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH YO'NALISHLARI	335
Narziyev Xayotjon Azamatovich	
O'ZBEKISTON SUG'URTA SOHASIDA RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALARNI QO'LLASH MASALALARI.....	343
Abdimuminova Saodat Taxirjonovna	
TO'QIMACHILIK SANOAT MAXSULOTLARI EKSPORT FAOLIYATI TAHLILI VA BRENDDA LIDERLIK TUSHUNCHALARI.....	352
Abdulazizova Xushnoza Nayabovna	
ИНСТИТУЦИОНАЛЬНО-ПРАВОВЫЕ МОДЕЛИ УПРАВЛЕНИЯ ОТХОДАМИ НА ОСНОВЕ ОПЫТА РАЗВИТЫХ СТРАН И ВОЗМОЖНОСТИ ИХ АДАПТАЦИИ В УСЛОВИЯХ УЗБЕКИСТАНА.....	357
Д. Мейлиева	
O'ZBEKISTON AUDITORLIK TIZIMIDA KASBDOSHLAR TOMONIDAN BAHOLASH (PEER REVIEW) TIZIMINI JORIY ETISH ISTIQBOLLARI	361
Parpiyev Jaxongir Iloxomjonovich	

ИСКУССТВЕННЫЙ ИНТЕЛЛЕКТ И БОЛЬШИЕ ДАННЫЕ (BIG DATA) В УПРАВЛЕНЧЕСКИХ РЕШЕНИЯХ.....	366
Шарипов Бахтиёр Михлибаевич	
O‘ZBEKISTONDA SUVGA BO‘LGAN TALABNI VAQTLI QATORLAR ORQALI TAHLIL QILISH	375
Sarvar Mamasoliyev	
BOSHQARUV VA NAZORAT MAQSADLARIDA XARAJATLAR HISOBINI TASHKIL ETISH	383
Isomuxamedov Akbarjon Boxodir o‘g‘li	
MINTAQALAR BARQAROR RIVOJLANISHINI TA‘MINLASHNING ASOSIY YO‘NALISHLARI.....	389
Salomat NOROVA	
O‘ZBEKISTON TURIZM BREND BOZORINING HOZIRGI HOLATI VA TENDENSIYALARI.....	394
Zufarov Akmal Gulamiddinovich	
INNOVATSION IQTISODIYOTDA QAYTA TIKLANUVCHI ENERGIYA MANBALARI SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH METODOLOGIYASI.....	404
Qodirov Baxodirjon Tursunovich	
O‘ZBEKISTON SOLIQ TIZIMINI MODERNIZATSIYA QILISHDA YAGONA INTERAKTIV DAVLAT XIZMATLARI PORTALINING O‘RNI VA AHAMIYATI	408
Dehqonov G‘ayratjon Raximovich	
OLIY TA‘LIM MUASSASALARIDA INNOVATSION HAMDA TIJORATLASHTIRISH MASALALARI	414
Inoyatov Mardonbek Mo‘min o‘g‘li	
OLIY IQTISODIY TA‘LIM ORQALI EKO-INNOVATSIYALAR VA “YASHIL” INVESTITSIYALARNI RAG‘BATLANTIRISH MEXANIZMLARI: SIYOSIY VA INSTITUTSIONAL DOIRALAR	418
Xasanova Zarina Maxamadaliyeva	
XODIMLAR MALAKASINI OSHIRISH — ZAMON TALABI.....	427
Narzullaev Oybek Narzullaevich	
BUXGALTERIYA HISOBINI YURITISHDA JURNAL-ORDER SHAKLINING AHAMIYATI.....	433
Axmedjanov Abdufoto	
KENDALL VA SPEARMAN TARTIBIY KORRELYATSIYA KOEFFITSIYENTLARI ASOSIDA YASHIL IQTISODIYOT INDIKATORLARINING STATISTIK O‘ZARO TA‘SIRINI MODELLASHTIRISH	437
Muradov Rustamjon Sobitxonovich	
ИНТЕНСИВНЫЕ И ЭКСТЕНСИВНЫЕ ОГРАНИЧЕНИЯ В РЕГУЛИРОВАНИИ СПРОСА.....	442
Аминджанова Румейса Батыровна, Камилова Наргиза Абдукажоревна	
ИНКЛЮЗИВНЫЙ ПОДХОД В ТУРИЗМЕ: ЗАРУБЕЖНЫЙ ОПЫТ И УЗБЕКСКАЯ ПРАКТИКА	445
Азимова Шахло Таировна	
AKSIYADORLIK JAMIYATLARIDA MOLIVAVIY HISOBOTNING XAQARO STANDARTLARIGA O‘TISHNING HOLATI VA TAHLILI	450
Bayjanov Sarsengaliy Xalmuratovich	
UZUM EKSPORT QILUVCHI KOMPANIYALARDA YASHIL O‘TISH JARAYONINI QO‘LLAB-QUVVATLASH UCHUN EKO-MARKETING VA AYLANMA IQTISODIYOT TAMOIYLLARINI INTEGRATSIYALASH.....	454
Usmonova Diyora Mahmud qizi	
UMUMTA‘LIM MAKTABLARIDA XARAJATLAR SMETASI VA SHTATLAR JADVALINING TAHLILI: OPTIMALLASHTIRISH VA SAMARADORLIKNING YANGICHA USULLARI (NAMANGAN VILOYATI MISOLIDA)	461
Umarov Avzaljon Yodgorali o‘g‘li	
INVESTITSIYALARNING KIRIB KELISHIGA TO‘SQINLIK QILUVCHI MUAMMOLARNI BARTARAF ETISH YO‘LLARI.....	467
Alimova Dilafro‘z Tohir qizi	
FARMATSEVIKA KORXONALARIDA MOLIVAVIY HISOBOT SHAKLLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH VA INVESTORLAR UCHUN AXBOROT OCHIQLIGINI TA‘MINLASH	470
Turdikulova Gulshad Nurmatovna	
ISHLAB CHIQRISH KORXONALARIDA MOLIVAVIY HISOBOTLARNING SHAFFOFLIGINI OSHIRISHDA MOLIVAVIY HISOBOTNING XALQARO STANDARTLARINING AHAMIYATI.....	477
Uztemirov Alisher Aktam o‘g‘li	

INNOVATSION IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA SANOAT TARMOQLARI RAQOBATBARDOSHLIGINI TA'MINLASHGA YO'NALTIRILGAN BANDLIK TUZILMASINI OPTIMALLASHTIRISH	482
Tursunov Bekmuxammad Omonovich	
XORIJ TAJRIBALARIDA SOLIQ BAZASINI ANIQLASH TARTIBI METODOLOGIYASINING MAVJUD METODLARI VA ULARNING XUSUSIYATLARI.....	489
Xalikchayeva Sadokat Ilxomjonovna	
IQTISODIY XAVFSIZLIKNING KONSEPTUAL ASOSLARI VA UNING MAMLAKAT IQTISODIYOTIDAGI O'RNI.....	496
Ramatillaev M.R.	
TIJORAT BANKLARIDA KREDIT RISKLARINI SUG'URTALASH VA DIVERSIFIKATSIYA QILISH MEKANIZMLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	502
Eshboyev Shahobiddin Anorqul o'g'li	
TIJORAT BANKLARI O'RTASIDAGI RAQOBATNI BAHOLASH VA KUCHAYTIRISHNING ZAMONAVIY METODOLOGIYASI: O'ZBEKISTON TAJRIBASI.....	506
Qulmetov Mansurbek Ro'zmatovich	
XALQARO REYTING TASHKILOTLARINING OLIY TA'LIM MUASSASALARIGA TA'SIRI VA MAVJUD PLATFORMALAR.....	515
O'rozboyev Xayrulla Murodboy o'g'li	
TALABALAR MOTIVATSIYASINING MEKANIZMLARI: LOYIHA ASOSIDAGI TA'LIM TEXNOLOGIYALARIDA.....	523
Kasimova (Mulladjanova) Nasiba Azimdjanovna	
ISH KUCHIDAN SAMARALI FOYDALANISH VA NORASMIY BANDLIKNI SOYADAN CHIQRARISH BO'YICHA TAKLIFLAR ISHLAB CHIQRISH	531
Pulatov Dilshod Xaqberdiyevich, Maxkamova Shaxlo Yulchiyevna, Absamatov Baxrom Danakulovich	
KASBIY TA'LIM MAZMUNIDA TA'LIM VA ISHLAB CHIQRARISH INTEGRATSIYASINI RAG'BATLANTIRISH ORQALI O'RTA BO'G'IN KADRLAR TAYYORLASHNING JOZIBADORLIGINI OSHIRISH YO'NALISHLARI	538
Tojiyev Sirojiddin Sayriddinovich	
O'ZBEKISTONDA TURIZM INFRATUZILMASINI BOSHQARISH TIZIMINING TURLARI VA SHAKLLARI.....	542
Muminova Mavjuda Sharifovna	
SUV RESURSLARIDAN FOYDALANISHNI STRATEGIK BOSHQARISH SAMARADORLIGI MASALALARI	547
Kadirhodjayeva Nilufar Rahmatullayevna	
MHXSGA MUVOFIQ ASOSIY VOSITALAR HISOBINI TASHKIL ETISH MASALALARI.....	552
Aliyev Sherzod Abdixomidovich	
ФАКТОРЫ ЭФФЕКТИВНОГО РАЗВИТИЯ ПРОИЗВОДСТВЕННОГО ПОТЕНЦИАЛА ПРОМЫШЛЕННЫХ ПРЕДПРИЯТИЙ.....	558
Аллаева Г.Ж.	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOTGA O'TISH SHAROITIDA INVESTITSION MUHITNI YAXSHILASH YO'NALISHLARI	564
Irisqulova Munisa Akmal qizi	
TASHABBUSLI BUDJET JARAYONLARI DOIRASIDA 2024-YILDA AMALGA OSHIRILGAN ISHLAR TAHLILI	569
Xamidov Xabibullo Xikmatulla o'g'li	
MINTAQA SANOATIDA AHOLI JON BOSHIGA YAQQ O'ZGARISHINING DINAMIK TAHLILI.....	574
Nabiyev G'ulom Abdusalomovich	
INFRATUZILMAVIY INVESTISIYA LOYIHALARINI DAVLAT-XUSUSIY SHERIKLIK ASOSIDA MOLIYALASHTIRISHDA RISKLARNI BOSHQARISHNING XORIJ TAJRIBALARI	583
Ergashev Axmadjon Maxmudjon o'g'li	
ПРОБЛЕМЫ ГЛОБАЛЬНОГО РАЗВИТИЯ ЗЕЛЕННОГО ФИНАНСИРОВАНИЯ В ЭКОЛОГИИ.....	587
Максудова Шахиста	

PAXTA-TO'QIMACHILIK KLASTERLARINING INVESTITSION FAOLLIGINI OSHIRISHNING ILMIY-USLUBIY JIHATLARI	593
B.Sh.Shadmanov	
ECONOMIC INDICATORS OF SUPPLY CHAIN EFFICIENCY IN UZBEKISTAN'S EXPORT SECTOR	597
Mukhammadiyaminova Shakhzoda Sherzodovna	
BUDJET TASHKILOTLARIDA BUDJETDAN TASHQARI MABLAG'LAR HISOBI VA ICHKI AUDITNI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	602
Muxtorova Maftuna Salohiddin qizi	
RAQAMLASHTIRISH JARAYONIDA BANKLARNING XAVFSIZLIGI VA MOLIYAVIY BARQARORLIGINI TA'MINLASHNING ILMIY-AMALIY ASOSLARI	607
Aliyeva Umidaxon Xusanboyevna	
XIZMATLAR SOHASI VA KAMBAG'ALLIK O'RTASIDAGI O'ZARO BOG'LIQLIK.....	611
Dawletmuratov Adilbay Mirzabaevich	
PROSPECTS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF INDUSTRIAL CLUSTERS BASED ON THE PRINCIPLES OF A "GREEN ECONOMY"	615
Boboqulov Sanjar Baxronkulovich, Kamolov Oybek Faxriddin o'g'li	
ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ ИНФОРМАЦИОННО-КОММУНИКАЦИОННЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ В СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИИ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ СВОБОДНЫХ ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКИХ ЗОН В НАЦИОНАЛЬНОЙ ЭКОНОМИКЕ	620
Халимжанов Дилшод Эргашбекович	
YASHIRIN IQTISODIYOTNI INNOVATSION RIVOJLANISHDAGI O'RNI VA O'ZIGA XOS XUSUSIYATLARI.....	626
Mavlyanov Muzaffar Yusupovich	
NAMANGAN VILOYATI TURIZM SOHASINING SO'NGGI YILLARDA RIVOJLANISHI VA STATISTIK TAHLILI	630
Kuymuratova Matlubaxon Abdimanabovna	
O'ZBEKISTON SHAROITIDA QISHLOQ XO'JALIGI MAHSULOTLARI EKSPORTINING IQTISODIY BARQARORLIGINI TA'MINLOVCHI OMILLAR TAHLILI	634
Faxriddinov Bahriddin	
INNOVATSION SHAROITDA TO'QIMACHILIK SANOATI RAQOBATBARDOSHLIGINI OSHIRISH	640
Sattarov Ilkhomjon Rahimjanovich	
IQLIM O'ZGARISHI SHAROITIDA SUV RESURSLARIDAN SAMARALI FOYDALANISH YO'LLARI.....	645
Nurmatov Norbek Jo'rayevich	
MINTAQA LOGISTIK XIZMAT KO'RSATISH SOHASINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING INNOVATSION VA INSTITUTSIONAL ISTIQBOLLARI	652
Xalimov Javlonbek Shaxriyorovich	
KORXONALARNING BANKROTLIK EHTIMOLINI SUN'IY INTELLEKT YORDAMIDA PROGNOZLASH	659
Zaynutdinov Ismoil Samariddin o'g'li	
АКТУАЛЬНЫЕ ВОПРОСЫ ЦИФРОВИЗАЦИИ ФИНАНСОВЫХ РЫНКОВ	665
Шомуродов Равшан Турсункулович	
MEDIA LOYIHALARINI BOSHQARISH: O'ZBEKISTON OAV AMALIYOTI TAHLILI	673
Yo'ldosheva Dilobar Jaxongir qizi	
O'QITISH NATIJALARINI ZAMONAVIY BAHOLASH TAMOYILLARI.....	677
Abdullayeva Sanobar Berdiyevna, Xujakulov Shaxriyor Shokir o'g'li	
MALAYZIYADA PROGRESSIV VA INKLYUZIV ISLOMIY MOLIYA TIZIMINI RIVOJLANTIRISH: 2024-YIL TAJRIBASI VA NATIJALARI	681
Safarova Nasiba Gulmurod qizi	
МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ОПЫТ ПРОВЕДЕНИЯ ПРОЦЕДУР ДЬЮ-ДИЛИДЖЕНС В АКЦИОНЕРНЫХ ОБЩЕСТВАХ.....	687
Прокудина Кристина Александровна	
HUDUDLARDA INVESTITSIYA SALOHİYATINI OSHIRISH YO'NALISHLARI	692
Xalilova Madinabonu Abduraxmon qizi	

LIZING MUOMALALARI HISOBINI XALQARO STANDARTLAR ASOSIDA TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	701
Baxadirov Alisher Komilovich	
TIJORAT BANKLARINING JISMONIY SHAXSLAR DEPOZITLARI VA ULARNI OPTIMALLASHTIRISH YO‘LLARI	705
Melikov Otabek Maxmadaminovich	
TIJORAT BANKLARIDA RAQAMLASHTIRISH VA EKOTIZIMNI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING AHAMIYATI	711
Erkinova Feruza Najmitdinovna	
DAVLAT SEKTORIDA ICHKI NAZORAT TIZIMINI BAHOLASHDA SUN‘IY INTELEKTDAN FOYDALANISH: XAVF YOKI IMKONIYAT	717
Ostonokulov Azamat Abdulkarimovich, Tadjiyev Erkin Muxitdinovich	
SUN‘IY VA KIMYOVIY TOLALARNING TO‘QIMACHILIK SANOATIDA EKOLOGIK BARQARORLIKNI TA‘MINLASHDAGI O‘RNI	723
Raximov Furqat Jalolovich	
OLIY TA‘LIM MASSASALARINING MOLIYAVIY RESURSLARINI BOSHQARISH MEXANIZMINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	728
Mahmudov Akbar Abduxamidovich	
TA‘LIM XIZMATLARI BOZORINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISHNING O‘ZIGA XOS XUSUSIYATLAR.....	733
Abdullayev Suyun Artikovich	
O‘ZBEKISTONDA AVTOMOBILSOZLIK KORXONALARIDA RAQAMLI TRANSFORMATSIYA JARAYONLARI: “UZAUTO MOTORS” AJ AMALIYOTI VA NATIJALARI.....	737
Allabergenov Azamat Joldasbayevich	
WAYS TO USE MARKETING DATA IN THE MANUFACTURING ENTERPRISE VALUATION PROCESS	742
Musayeva Shoira Azimovna, Usmonova Dilfuza Ilkhomovna	
KICHIK SANOAT KORXONALARI O‘RTASIDAGI ISHLAB CHIQARISH VA KOOPERATIV ALOQALAR HOLATI.....	747
Boyturayev Olimjon Urayimovich	
BANK RISKLARI VA ULARNI TA‘SIRINI EKONOMETRIK MODELLASHTIRISHDA STATISTIK HISOBTLARNI SHAKLLANTIRISHNING NAZARIY ASOSLARI	753
Kamoldinov Sardorbek Maxammadsobir o‘g‘li	
O‘ZBEKISTONDA AYOLLARNING ISH BILAN BANDLIGINI OSHIRISH IMKONIYATLARI	761
Eshqobulova Charos O‘roq qizi	
O‘ZBEKISTONNING BARQAROR RIVOJLANISH KONSEPSIYASI: TARIXIY MEROS VA ZAMONAVIY YASHIL TEXNOLOGIYALAR UYG‘UNLIGI.....	766
Azimova Shohista Salohiddinovna	
SOLIQ TIZIMIDA RAQAMLI MARKIROVKALANGAN TOVARLARNI RAQAMLASHTIRISHNI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH MUAMMOLARI	770
Muxammadov Nodir Karimovich	
BIZNES JARAYONLARINI OPTIMALLASHTIRISHDA “LEAN MANAGEMENT” TIZIMINI JORIY ETISHNING ILMIY ASOSLARI	775
Muhiddinov Ozodbek Ikromjon o‘g‘li, Shakirova Gulrux Po‘latjon qizi, Ozodbek Musayev	
QORAQALPOG‘ISTON RESPUBLIKASINING TURISTIK POTENTIALI UMUMIY TAVSIFI.....	783
Madaminova Sanobar Askarovna	
KICHIK BIZNES KORXONALARIDA EKSPORT MAHSULOTLARI ISHLAB CHIQARISH KONSEPSIYASINI SHAKLLANTIRISH VA RIVOJLANTIRISH YO‘NALISHLARI.....	789
Boymirzayev Zokirjon Mashrabboyevich	
AHOLINING TURMUSH DARAJASI VA UNING KO‘RSATKICHLARI.....	794
Sayitbayev Shermirza Datkamirzayevich	
KORXONA ASOSIY XO‘JALIK YURITUVCHI SUBYEKT SIFATIDA AHAMIYATI.....	799
Yuldashova Yoqutoy Murodjon qizi, Yuldashev Abduhakim Abdulkarimovich	
DAVLAT ISHTIROKIDAGI KORXONALARNI XUSUSIYLASHTIRISH JARAYONIDA KADRLAR SALOHIYATINI SAQLAB QOLISH VA RIVOJLANTIRISH STRATEGIYALARI.....	803
Bekchanov Ruslan Ambiyatovich	

PARALLEL KORPUS ASOSIDA INGLIZ VA O'ZBEK TILLARIDA QISHLOQ XO'JALIK ATAMALARINING EKVALENTLIK XUSUSIYATLARI	807
Yulduz Xalilova Nasriddinovna	
KOLBASA VA GO'SHT MAHSULOTLARI ISHLAB CHIQRISHDA CHIQUINDISIZ ISHLAB CHIQRISH ("ZERO WASTE") MODELINING ROLI: XORIJIY TAJRIBA VA O'ZBEKISTON SHAROITIDAGI AMALIY YO'NALISHLAR.....	810
Eshtemirova Anora Norboy qizi	
EKSPORTYOR KORXONALARDA TOVAR VA XIZMATLAR EKSPORTI BO'YICHA QO'SHILGAN QIYMAT VA FOYDA SOLIG'INI TO'G'RI HISOBLANISHI TAHLILI VA ISTIQBOLLARI.....	814
Sobirova Xilola Rustam qizi	
O'ZBEKISTONDA TO'QIMACHILIK VA TIKUV-TRIKOTAJ SANOATI RIVOJLANISHINING MILLIY RAQOBATBARDOSHLIKNI OSHIRISHDAGI O'RNI	819
Ikramova Taxmina Latifovna	
YANGI RIVOJLANAYOTGAN BOZORLARIDA HR QAROR QABUL QILISH JARAYONINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISHDA IQTISODIY TA'LIMNING ROLI	824
Dilfuza Shokirova	
UZOQ MUDDATLI AKTIVLAR HISOBINI XALQARO BUXGALTERIYA STANDARTLARI ASOSIDA TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	833
Abdiev Mutolib Anvar o'g'li	
DAVLAT-XUSUSIY SHERIKLIK TIZIMINING NAZARIY VA USLUBIY ASOSLARI	838
Raximjonova Shohsanam Baxodirovna	
AKTIVLAR VA MAJBURIYATLARNI MHXS ASOSIDA BAHOLASHNING ZARURIYATI VA AHAMIYATI	842
G'anibayev Iloxomjon Shokiraliyevich	
XORIJIY INVESTITSIYALARNI JALB QILISH JARAYONINING O'ZIGA XOS XUSUSIYATLARI VA HUDUDIY IQTISODIY RIVOJLANISH BILAN BOG'LIQLIGI	847
Xamidova Faridaxon Abdulkarim qizi, Turdimuratova Aziza Alisherovna	
AGRAR ISHLAB CHIQRISHNI BARQAROR RIVOJLANTIRISHDA "QISHLOQ XO'JALIGI-4.0" VA "AQLLI QISHLOQ XO'JALIGI" KONSEPSIYALARIDAN SAMARALI FOYDALANISH.....	851
Yusupov Muxiddin Soatovich	
PAXTA-TO'QIMACHILIK KLASTERLARINI MOLIYALASHTIRISH MANBALARINI GURUHLASH VA BAHOLASH.....	860
Davlyatov Bekzodjon Aslanxojayevich	
TA'LIM TIZIMINI INNOVATSION RIVOJLANTIRISHDA XORIY TAJRIBASINING AHAMIYATI	864
Sobirov Shaxzod Ozod o'g'li	
O'ZBEKISTONDA TADBIRKORLIK SUBYEKTLARINI SOLIQQA TORTISHNI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH MASALALARI	868
Karimov Mirolimjon Karimjon o'g'li	
ПРОБЛЕМЫ МЕЖДУНАРОДНОГО ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОГО СОТРУДНИЧЕСТВА В ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОМ РАЗВИТИИ УЗБЕКИСТАНА.....	875
Аликулов С. А., Хамракулова О. Д.	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOTDA KORXONALAR BOSHQARUV MEKANIZMLARINING EVOLYUTSIYASI: KONSEPTUAL TAHLIL.....	880
Nabiev Bobur Muhammadqosim o'g'li	
SUD-HUQUQ TIZIMINI YANADA DEMOKRATLASHTIRISH: JORIY HOLATI, MUAMMOLAR VA ISTIQBOLLAR.....	884
Majidov Muslimbek Maxamadjon o'g'li	
IQTISODIYOTNI LIBERALLASHTIRISH SHAROITIDA QISHLOQ XO'JALIGIDA KLASTERLARNI TASHKIL ETISHNING TASHKILIIY-HUQUQIY ASOSLARI.....	889
Xo'jageldiyev Chorshanbi Pardayevich	
O'ZBEKISTONDA YASHIL TURIZMNI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA ZAMONAVIY INNOVATSION TEXNOLOGIYALARDAN FOYDALANISH.....	893
Shaymanova Nigora Yusupovna	

XO'JALIK FAOLIYATINI SAMARADORLIGI VA BIZNES HOLATINI BAHOLASH	899
Abdulkarimova Muslima Abduaziz qizi, Yuldashev Abduhakim Abdulkarimovich	
CROSS-BORDER E-COMMERCE IN CENTRAL ASIA.....	904
Bakhtiyorjon Komilov	
O'ZBEKISTONDA NORASMIY SEKTOR ISHCHILARINING PENSIYA TA'MINOTI MASALALARI.....	908
Abdulazizova Nargiza Baxodir qizi	
KORXONA VA TASHKILOTLARDA QOG'UZ SARFINI OPTIMALLASHTIRISHDA JAHON TAJRIBASI	913
Oripov Mirzo Mahmudovich	
ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ ИСКУССТВЕННОГО ИНТЕЛЛЕКТА В ЗАЩИТЕ ВНУТРЕННЕГО РЫНКА ОТ КОНТРАФАКТНОЙ ПРОДУКЦИИ (НА ПРИМЕРЕ РЕСПУБЛИКИ УЗБЕКИСТАН).....	917
Ибраимова Махсура Уснатдин кизи	
KICHIK BIZNES VA TADBIRKORLIK SUBYEKTLARIDA BOSHQARUV TIZIMINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH YO'NALISHLARI	922
Xasanova Robiyaxon Kamoliddin qizi	
THE IMPACT OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE TECHNOLOGIES ON THE PROCESSES OF DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION IN THE INSURANCE INDUSTRY.....	927
D.D.Omonova	
THE ROLE OF INTERNATIONAL FINANCIAL INSTITUTIONS IN THE GLOBAL ECONOMY AND THEIR STAGES OF DEVELOPMENT.....	933
Yovkochev Sherzod	
YURIDIK SHAXSLARNI YIRIK SOLIQ TO'LOVCHILAR TOIFASIGA KIRITISH MEZONLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH YO'LLARI.....	941
To'raqulov Bekzod Hazratqul o'g'li	
BUTUNJAHON SAVDO TASHKILOTIGA A'ZO BO'LISHDA SOLIQ TIZIMINI TRANSFORMATSIYA QILISHNI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH MASALALARI.....	945
Xojjakbar Zaynabidinov	
BANK TIZIMIDA TAVAKKALCHILIK TUSHUNCHASI VA UNI BAHOLASHNING ZAMONAVIY YONDASHUVLARI	950
Malikova Dilrabo Muminovna, Shakarova Kumush Faxriddin qizi	
REAL SEKTOR TARMOQLARINI KREDITLASHDA MOLIVAVIY BARQARORLIKNI TA'MINLASH YO'LLARI.....	955
Savurbayev Zafar Abdumuminovich	
INVESTITSIYA JOZIBADORLIGINI OSHIRISHDA IQTISODIY BARQARORLIK OMILLARI VA ULARNING BOSHQARUVI	960
D. G. Bazarov	
YANGI O'ZBEKISTONDA DAVLAT-XUSUSIY SHERIKLIK SOHASINI YANADA TAKOMILLASHTIRISH HAMDA KOMPLEKS TIZIMLASHTIRISH	966
Abdullayev Javohir Abdumalik o'g'li	
XIZMATLAR KO'RSATISH KORXONALARIDA INNOVATSIYA FAOLIYATINI SAMARALI TASHKIL ETISH VA BOSHQARISH: IQTISODIY TAHLIL VA ISTIQBOLLI TAVSIYALAR	971
Xudayberdiyeva Nargiza Nizomiddin qizi	
MINTAQADA KICHIK BIZNES KORXONALARI SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH MEXANIZMLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	976
Ergashev Jamshid Jamoliddinovich	
TADBIRKORLIK SUBYEKTLARIDA INNOVATSION MAHSULOTLARNI ISHLAB CHIQRISHNI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH YO'LLARI.....	981
Mirzayev Kobil Nosirjonovich	
PUL AYLANMASINI TASHKIL QILISHNING XORIJ TAJRIBASI VA O'ZBEKISTONDA FOYDALANISHNING IMKONIYATLARI.....	987
Gadoyev So'hrob Jumakulovich	
MARKETING VA TOVAR STRATEGIYALARINI ISHLAB CHIQISH	993
Ibadullayeva Sevara Allashukurovna, Yuldashev Abduhakim Abdulkarimovich	

PILLACHILIK SOHASINI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA INVESTITSIYA VA DAVLAT KO'MAGIGA OID METODOLOGIK YONDASHUVLAR.....	998
<i>Xudoykulov Mamarasul Radjabovich</i>	
SURXONDARYO VILOYATIDAGI KICHIK BIZNES VA TADBIRKORLIKNING QURILISH SOHASIDAGI ULUSHNING TREND MODELLARI ORQALI TAHLILI.....	1005
<i>Mamatkulova Xurshida Nasrullayevna</i>	
THEORETICAL AND METHODOLOGICAL BASES OF TEXTILE PRODUCTS MARKET SEGMENTATION.....	1012
<i>Ibaydullaeva Feruza Kholjuraevna</i>	
O'ZBEKISTONNING JINOIY FAOLIYATDAN OLINGAN DAROMADLARNI LEGALLASHTIRISHGA QARSHI KURASH TIZIMIGA SUN'YI INTELLEKTNI INTEGRATSIYASI: BANK SEKTORIDA JORIY ETISHNING POTENSIALI VA TO'SIQLARINI BAHOLASH.....	1018
<i>Rashidov Avazbek Raximovich</i>	
UZOQ MUDDATLI AKTIVLAR HISOBINI XALQARO STANDARTLAR ASOSIDA TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	1025
<i>Shermatov Sirojiddan Xaydarovich</i>	
РОЛЬ ИСКУССТВЕННОГО ИНТЕЛЛЕКТА В УСОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИИ ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОЙ РЕЗУЛЬТАТИВНОСТИ КОМПОНЕНТОВ ПРОЕКТА «БЕЗОПАСНЫЙ ГОРОД».....	1029
<i>Иминов Акбаржон Одилжонович</i>	
XIZMAT KO'RSATISH TARMOQLARIDA BOSHQARUV SALOHİYATINI OSHIRISH.....	1034
<i>Tleubergenov Raxat Shahibaevich</i>	
THE ROLE OF ESG IN ADVANCING CORPORATE REFORMS IN UZBEKISTAN.....	1038
<i>Zakhidov Azizbek Rustamovich</i>	
O'ZBEKISTONDA MARKETING ROLI ORQALI IQTISODIY SIYOSATGA TA'SIRI.....	1043
<i>Egamberdiyev Muzaffar</i>	
DAVLAT BUDJETI JARAYONINI OPTIMALLASHTIRISH YO'NALISHLARI: XALQARO TAJRIBA VA O'ZBEKISTON AMALIYOTI.....	1046
<i>Nosirov Islombek Xurram o'g'li</i>	
O'ZBEKISTONDA JISMONIY SHAXSLARDAN OLINADIGAN DAROMAD SOLIG'INING PROGRESSIV STAVKASINI JORIY ETISH MEXANIZMI.....	1052
<i>Pulatov Dilshod Xaqberdiyevich, Mamatkulov Salimjon Raxmonkulovich, Xujamuradov Abrorbek Ro'zimurat o'g'li, Otabekov Otajon G'ayrat o'g'li, Abdiyev Mansur Musurmonovich</i>	
KORXONANING MODDIY BAZASI.....	1060
<i>Ozodova Shahzoda Ulug'bek qizi</i>	
FINTECH-STARTAPLAR VA TIJORAT BANKLARI HAMKORLIGI: SINERGETIK INTEGRATSIYA VA INNOVATSION EKOTIZIM SHAKLLANISHI.....	1064
<i>Normo'minov Temurbek Sheraliyevich</i>	
DAVLAT FUQAROLIK XIZMATCHILARINING MEHNATIGA HAQ TO'LASHDA YANGI YAGONA TARIF SETKASINI JORIY ETISH MASALALARI.....	1069
<i>Oqiljonov Azizjon Olimjon o'g'li</i>	
ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ РАЗВИТИЯ ДИСТАНЦИОННЫХ БАНКОВСКИХ УСЛУГ В УСЛОВИЯХ ЦИФРОВИЗАЦИИ.....	1074
<i>Хасилова Висола Шоохоровна</i>	
HARD WORK, INDEBTEDNESS AND HOPE: A SOCIO-ECONOMIC LOOK OF MODERN LABOR.....	1078
<i>Rakhmatullayev Sarvar Nazar o'g'li, Abdukarimova Muborak Sharaf qizi, Madrakhimova R. G.</i>	
KORXONALARDA ISHLAB CHIQRISH XARAJATLARI VA ULARNI HISOBGA OLISH.....	1085
<i>Muradova Minavvar Izzatullayevna</i>	
O'ZBEKISTONDA AKT SOHASINING HOZIRGI HOLATI VA RIVOJLANISH DINAMIKASI: SAMARADORLIKNI BAHOLASH VA RAQAMLASHTIRISHNING MUAMMOLARI.....	1089
<i>Salibaev Xabibullo Negmatullaxanovich</i>	
TIJORAT BANK KREDIT PORTFELINING SIFAT BOSHQARUV SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH YO'LLARI.....	1094
<i>G'aybullayev Odil Baxtiyarovich, Amanova Xurshida Inyatullaevna</i>	

XIZMAT KO'RSATISH SOHASIDA O'ZINI-O'ZI BAND QILISH ORQALI KAMBAG'ALLIKNI PASAYTIRISH MASALALARI	1099
<i>Azimova Hulkar Egamberdiyevna</i>	
СОКРАЩЕНИЕ БЕДНОСТИ КАК СОЦИАЛЬНАЯ СОСТАВЛЯЮЩАЯ ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОЙ РЕФОРМЫ УЗБЕКИСТАНА.....	1103
<i>Амирджанова Ситора Суннат кизи</i>	
IQTISODIY JARAYONLARNI BOSHQARISHDA OPTIMALLASHTIRISH MODELLARI VA ULARNING NAZARIY-USLUBIY ASOSLARI	1108
<i>Ibragimov Nodir Nusriddinovich</i>	
MARKETINGDAGI ISTE'MOLCHILAR MOTIVATSIYASIDA NAFLILIK NAZARIYALARIDAN FOYDALANISH.....	1113
<i>Jalilov Jamshid G'anijonovich</i>	
AHOLI ZICH HUDUDLARDA KICHIK BIZNESNI RIVOJLANTIRISHINING HOZIRGI HOLATI TAHLILI ANDIJON VILOYAT MISOLIDA	1119
<i>Karimov Abdusamat Ismonovich, Bo'stonova Nilufar Abdusmatovna</i>	
CHAKANA SAVDO KORXONALARIDA ISTE'MOLCHILAR XULQ-ATVORINING SAVDO HAJMIGA TA'SIRINING TAHLILI	1125
<i>Haydarova Mohichehra Xurram qizi</i>	
BOSHQARUV TIZIMINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISHDA AXBOROT-KOMMUNIKATSION TEXNOLOGIYALARNING O'RNI.....	1131
<i>Haydarov Husanboy Ahmadjon o'g'li</i>	
DAVLAT QARZINING IQTISODIY O'SISHGA TA'SIRI: PANEL MA'LUMOTLAR TAHLILI.....	1135
<i>Sanakulova B. R., Jamolov M.M.</i>	
AUTSORSING FAOLIYATINI MOLIYALASHTIRISH MEKANIZMLARI	1148
<i>Xamidov Anis Choriyevich</i>	
BIOCHEMICAL CHANGES IN THE BODY DURING THE PERIOD OF FATIGUE AND REST AFTER WORK FOR ATHLETES	1153
<i>Yoldasheva Roila Jumaevna, Ruyobova Shakhlo Anvar qizi</i>	
KICHIK BIZNESNI RIVOJLANTIRISHGA OID XORIJIY MAMLAKATLARNING ILG'OR NAZARIYALARI VA YONDASHUVLARI	1159
<i>Muradova Nazira Raximjanovna</i>	
XORAZMDA IQTISODIY BARQARORLIK MEKANIZMLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	1165
<i>Xudayorova Munira Omonboy qizi</i>	
QURILISH MATERIALLARI SANOATIDA INNOVATSION BUXGALTERIYA HISOBINI JORIY ETISH	1170
<i>Mirzayev Komiljon Abdullajonovich</i>	
SOLIQ MA'MURCHILIGI MEKANIZMINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH ORQALI SOLIQ SOLISH BAZASINI KENGAYTIRISH IMKONIYATLARI	1175
<i>Jononmirzayeva Dilafruz Ilhom qizi</i>	
ИЗБАВЛЕНИЕ ОТ ИНФЛЯЦИИ С ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕМ ЦИФРОВЫХ МЕТОДОВ И МАТЕМАТИЧЕСКИХ МОДЕЛЕЙ В СФЕРЕ ИНФОРМАЦИОННЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ	1180
<i>Абидов А.А., Ахраров Б.С., Паязов М.М., Ахмедов А.М.</i>	
O'ZBEKISTONDA YOSHLAR TADBIRKORLIGINI RIVOJLANTIRISH VA INNOVATSION BIZNES TASHABBUSLARINI QO'LLAB-QUVVATLASH MEKANIZMLARI.....	1185
<i>Karimova Mavjuda Boxodirovna</i>	
INVESTITSIYA MUHITINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH ORQALI YUQORI TEXNOLOGIYALI TARMOQLARNI RIVOJLANTIRISH VA IQTISODIY BARQARORLIKNI TA'MINLASH.....	1189
<i>Raxmatova Nargizaxon A'zamxonovna</i>	
O'ZBEKISTONDA ELEKTRON PULGA O'TISH ISTIQBOLLARI, KORRUPSIYA VA YASHIRIN IQTISODIYOTGA QARSHI KURASHISHDA KUTILAYOTGAN SAMARADORLIK	1195
<i>Pulatov Dilshod Xaqberdiyevich, Abdiyev Mansur Musurmonovich</i>	
KICHIK BIZNES TADBIRKORLIK SUBYEKTLARINI IQTISODIY XAVFSIZLIGI MASALALARI.....	1202
<i>Anafiyayev Abdurashid Mamasidiqovich</i>	

RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALAR ASOSIDA ISHLAB CHIQRISH XARAJATLARI HISOBINI AVTOMATLASHTIRISH	1206
Xusinov Ibragim Ismoilovich	
ЭВОЛЮЦИЯ ТОРГОВОЙ ПОЛИТИКИ ТУРЦИИ В КОНТЕКСТЕ ИНТЕГРАЦИИ В ГЛОБАЛЬНЫЕ ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКИЕ ЦЕПОЧКИ	1210
Солиев Абдумаджид Джабборович	
MAKTABGACHA TA'LIM TASHKILOTI DIREKTORINING MOLIVAVIY SAVODXONLIGI: NAZARIYA VA AMALIYOTI.....	1215
Abdullayeva Nafisa Shavkatovna, Boymuradov Normurod Abdusodikovich	
TADBIRKORLIK SUBYEKTLARIGA MOLIVAVIY HIMOYA XIZMATLARI KO'RSATISHNING SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH YO'LLARI	1220
G'aniyeva Nozima Alijon qizi	
ОЦЕНКА ПОТЕНЦИАЛА КЛАСТЕРИЗАЦИИ КОКОНОПЕРЕРАБАТЫВАЮЩИХ ПРЕДПРИЯТИЙ НА ШЕЛКОВОМ ОТРАСЛИ УЗБЕКИСТАНА.....	1225
Ходжиматов Равшанбек Расулжанович	
XIZMAT KO'RSATISH SOHASIDA ISH BILAN BANDLIK SHAKLLANISHINING XORIY TAJRIBASI	1231
Abdusaidov Akmal Abduvaliyevich	
TEMIR YO'L TRANSPORTI KORXONALARIDA MOLIVAVIY-IQTISODIY BOSHQARUV SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH UCHUN KONTROLLING VOSITALARINI JORIY ETISH.....	1236
Kayumov Zafarbek Odil o'g'li	
BANK HR JARAYONLARIDA SUN'YI INTELLEKTNI QO'LLASH IMKONIYATLARI.....	1243
D. DJabbarova	
MEHNAT BOZORIDA NORASMIY BANDLIKNI QISQARTIRISH MEXANIZMLARI	1247
Mirzakarimova Muyassarxon Muminovna	
IJTIMOIIY XIZMATLAR TIZIMIDA DAVLAT VA NODAVLAT SEKTORINING O'ZARO ALOQASI HAMDA XORIJIY TAJRIBA TAHLILI.....	1251
Berdiyeva Nafisa Qahramonovna	
ПРИМЕНЕНИЕ КОНТРОЛЛИНГА В ОРГАНИЗАЦИОННО-ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОЙ СИСТЕМЕ УПРАВЛЕНИЯ ЖЕЛЕЗНОДОРОЖНОГО ТРАНСПОРТА	1257
Каюмов Зафарбек Одил угли	
BILVOSITA SOLIQLAR HISOBINI TASHKIL ETISHDA SOLIQ NAZORATINING AHAMIYATI	1263
Djalilov Rahmonkul Hamidovich	
INVESTITSION FAOLIYATNING IQTISODIY MOHIYATI VA UNING SANOAT RIVOJLANISHIDAGI O'RNI	1268
Yuldoshev Sobir Fayzullayevich	
O'ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASI IQTISODIYOTINING TRANSFORMATSIYASI SHAROITIDA AHOLI DAROMADLARINING TAQSIMOT TAHLILI.....	1272
Bayxonov Baxodirjon Tursunbayevich	
TIJORAT BANKLARIDA RAQAMLI MARKETINGNI QO'LLASHNING XORIY TAJRIBASI.....	1277
Raxmatova Shaxnoza Rustamovna, Ochilova Dilnoza Ismoil qizi	
ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ УСТОЙЧИВОЙ ЗАНЯТОСТИ В ПРОМЫШЛЕННОСТИ В УСЛОВИЯХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ ПРЕОБРАЗОВАНИЙ	1283
Б.С. Разакова	
ZAMONAVIY TURISTIK KLASTERLARNI BOSHQARISHNING NAZARIY-USLUBIY ASOSLARI	1289
Azim Pulatov	
O'ZBEKISTONDA YOSHLAR BANDLIGINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH YO'NALISHLARI VA DAVLAT SIYOSATINING SAMARADORLIGI	1296
Qodirov Baxodirjon Shuhratovich	
YASHIL TEXNOLOGIYALAR ASOSIDA SANOAT KORXONALARINING ISHLAB CHIQRISH SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISHDA RAQAMLI TRANSFORMATSIYANING AHAMIYATI	1302
Ergashev Sanjarbek Sobirjon o'g'li	
ONLAYN TA'LIM PLATFORMALARI INTERAKTIV CHATBOTLARI SAMARADORLIGINI KOMPLEKS BAHOLASH	1306
Zaripova Mukaddas Djumayozovna, Yusupova Asila Xidirqul qizi	

TO'QIMACHILIK SANOATI KORXONALARINING MOLIVAVIY BARQARORLIGINI BAHOLASHNING TAKOMILLASHTIRILGAN USLUBIYOTI	1313
Abdullayeva Sevaraxon Xasanovna	
ZARAFSHON MINTAQASI HUDUDLARIDA IQTISODIY MUTANOSIBLIKKA TA'SIR ETUVCHI OMILLAR TAHLILI VA ULARNING O'ZGARISH TENDENSIYALARI	1320
Murtazayev Isabek Bazarbayevich	
O'ZBEKISTONDA AHOLI TURMUSH DARAJASINI YAXSHILASHNI MOLIVAVIY MANBALARI	1327
Mansurov Mansur Alisherovich, Xolbekova Dilobarxon Rasuljon qizi	
O'ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASIDA MONETAR SIYOSATNING TRANSMISSIYA MEXANIZMLARI SAMARADORLIGI.....	1330
Boltayeva Nilufar Shavkat qizi	
HUDUDIY TURIZM RIVOJLANISHIDA BARQAROR BOSHQARUV STRATEGIYALARINI ISHLAB CHIQUISH	1336
Barakayev Elbekjon Abdulla o'g'li	
O'ZBEKISTON TA'LIM TIZIMIDA DAVLAT-XUSUSIY SHERIKLIK MEXANIZMINI JORIY ETISH.....	1343
Yuldashev Kodirjon Mamadjanovich	
ILG'OR XORIJIY DAVLATLAR TAJRIBASIDA BOSHQARUV XODIMLARI QOBILİYATLARIDAN FOYDALANISH ORQALI KORXONA SALOHİYATINI YUKSALTIRISH YO'LLARI	1348
Ayubxon Qutbiddinov Bosit o'g'li	
INTEGRATSIYALASHGAN XARAJATLAR TAHLILI: ISHLAB CHIQUARISH VA LOGISTIKA XARAJATLARINING MAHSULOT TANNARXIGA TA'SIRI	1353
Zokirjonov Asadbek Otabek o'g'li, Xashimova Zuhraxon Kahramonovna	
QASHQADARYO VILOYATI SANOATINI INNOVATSION RIVOJLANTIRISH STRATEGIYASINING ASOSIY YO'NALISHLARI VA ULARNI EKONOMETRIK MODELLAR YORDAMIDA BAHOLASH	1358
Raxmatullayev Doston Asad o'g'li	
MAKTABGACHA TA'LIM MUASSASALARIDA BOLALAR TA'MINOTIGA OTA-ONALAR TOMONIDAN HAQ TO'LASH VA UN DAN FOYDALANISH TARTIBINING BUXGALTERIYA HISOBI.....	1361
Ro'ziboyev Oybek Baxromovich	
KICHIK BIZNESNING HUDUDIY ISH BILAN BANDLIKKA TA'SIRI.....	1367
Qulmatov Alimjan Abdulloyevich	
INDUSTRIYA 4.0 SHAROITIDA KASBLAR TARKIBI TUZILMASI VA KOMPETENSIYALAR TRANSFORMATSIYASI	1371
Mirzakarimova Muyassarxon Muminovna	
RAQAMLI IDENTIFIKATSIYA (E-ID) TIZIMINING G'AZNACHILIK OPERATSIYALARIDA QO'LLANISH ISTIQBOLLARI	1375
Raximov Shaxzod Maxsudjanovich	
IQTISODIYOTNI RAQAMLI TRANSFORMATSIYALASH SHAROITIDA AVTOMOBIL SANOATI KORXONALARINING INVESTITSION FAOLIYATINI STRATEGIK RIVOJLANTIRISH	1380
Kasimova Nozima Omilovna	
METHODOLOGY FOR ASSESSING THE EFFECTIVE PERFORMANCE OF AN INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISE IN THE CONTEXT OF INDUSTRY 4.0.....	1384
Kudaynazarova Dilnaz Koshkarbaevna	
TEACHING PROGRAMMING COLLABORATIVELY THROUGH GOOGLE COLAB AND GITHUB INTEGRATION	1388
Saidova Dilfuza Ergashovna	
O'ZBEKISTONDA BARQAROR IQTISODIY O'SISHNI TA'MINLASHNING ASOSIY YO'NALISHLARI	1392
Djumayev Zayniddin Axmedovich	
ЦИФРОВАЯ МОДЕРНИЗАЦИЯ СИСТЕМЫ ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ УЗБЕКИСТАНА: КОНЦЕПТУАЛЬНАЯ ОСНОВА И КЛЮЧЕВЫЕ ОРИЕНТИРЫ	1397
Киличева Феруза Бешимовна	
ТРАНСФОРМАЦИЯ КОНСТИТУЦИОННЫХ НОРМ О СОБСТВЕННОСТИ И ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОЙ СВОБОДЕ В УЗБЕКИСТАНА В УСЛОВИЯХ СОЦИАЛЬНОГО ГОСУДАРСТВА	1401
Абдуллаева Мавлюда Садыковна	

KICHIK BIZNES VA TADBIRKORLIKNI INNOVATSION IQTISODIYOTDA QO'LLAB-QUVVATLASH STRATEGIYALARI.....	1407
Mirzaaxmedov Nodirbek Shavkatovich	
KORXONALAR RAQOBATBARDOSHLIGINI TAHLIL QILISH VA MARKETING STRATEGIYASINI TANLASH	1414
Yoqubjonova Dildora Timur qizi	
TURISTIK XIZMATLAR BOZORINING XUSUSIYATLARI VA BRENDLASH IMKONIYATLARI	1420
Yusupova Moxinur Farxod qizi	
TA'LIM TASHKILOTLARIDA MOLIYAVIY AKTIVLARNI BOSHQARISH.....	1428
Meliboyev Ibroxim Mavlon o'g'li	
SOLIQ NAZORATINI TASHKIL ETISHDA XALQARO TAJRIBA VA O'ZBEKISTONGA TATBIQ ETISH IMKONIYATLARI.....	1432
Kodirov Aqliddin Xakim o'g'li	
AVTOMOBIL SAVDOSIDA ZAMONAVIY MARKETING KONSEPSIYALARINING QO'LLANILISHI	1437
Adamboyev Abror Akrom o'g'li, Akramov T.A.	
CHARM-POYABZAL KORXONALARIDA RESURSLARDAN MUQOBIL FOYDALANISH SAMARADORLIK KO'RSATKICHLARINI PROGNOZLASH.....	1443
Otaniyozov Orifjon Otaxonovich	
BANK KAPITALI YETARLILIGI VA RISKLARNI BOSHQARISH TIZIMINING SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH MEXANIZMLARI	1449
Abdusalamov Olimjon Eshmirzayevich	
SIRKULYAR IQTISODIYOTDA RESURS TANQISLIGINING OLDINI OLISH MASALALARI	1454
Ismoilova Gulchiroy Tolliboy qizi	
ICHKI AUDIT VA UNING KORXONA NAZORAT TIZIMIDAGI O'RNI: MUAMMO VA YECHIMLAR.....	1472
Mexmonaliyev Ulug'bek Erkinjon o'g'li	
QISHLOQ XO'JALIGIDA RISK TURLARI VA KELIB CHIQUISH OMILLARI	1477
Xamrokulov Sindor Qahramonovich	
O'ZBEKISTONDA TURISTLARGA OVQATLANISH XIZMATLARINI KO'RSATISHNI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING BOSHQARUV MEXANIZMINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	1483
Maxmadiyeva Charos Xayrullayevna	
TIJORAT BANKLARINING MOLIYAVIY BARQARORLIGINI TA'MINLASHNING SAMARALI YO'LLARI.....	1487
Adilov Mirkomil Miralimovich	
BUDJET JARAYONIDA OCHIQLIK VA SHAFFOFLIKNI OSHIRISH MEXANIZMLARINING AMALDAGI HOLATI VA RIVOJLANISH ISTIQBOLLARI	1494
Shernayev Akbar Aqmirzayevich	
KICHIK TADBIRKORLIK LOYIHALARINI MOLIYALASHTIRISHDA BANK KREDITLARI SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH OMILLARI	1499
Norqobilova Nargiza Abdiqodirovna	
OLIY TA'LIM XIZMATLARI BOZORIDA NODAVLAT OLIY TA'LIM MUASSASALARINING ISHTIROKI VA ULARDA MARKETING FAOLIYATINI RIVOJLANTIRISH	1504
Yuldashov Isomiddin Sidiqovich	
МАКРОЭКОНОМИЧЕСКАЯ ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТЬ ОПТИМИЗАЦИИ НАЛОГОВЫХ ПОСТУПЛЕНИЙ И ЕЁ ЗНАЧЕНИЕ ДЛЯ ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОГО РАЗВИТИЯ.....	1509
Муталова Дилором Махамаджановна, Хакимова Ситора Ильёсжон кизи	
RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA TELEKOMMUNIKATSIYA XIZMATLARI BOZORINI RIVOJLANTIRISH TENDENSIYALARI VA MEXANIZMLARI.....	1515
Suyunov Asror Baxtiyorovich	
INNOVATSION FAOLIYATNI RAG'BATLANTIRISHDA DAVLATNING O'RNI.....	1518
Saitkamolov Muxammadxo'ja Sobirxo'ja o'g'li	
SOLIQ MA'MURIYATCHILIGINING MOHIYATI VA UNING TADBIRKORLIK MUHITIDAGI O'RNI.....	1521
Xurramov Azizbek Muxiddin o'g'li	

DETERMINATION OF SEED DAMAGE IN THE PNEUMATIC TRANSPORT SYSTEM BY CONDUCTING EXPERIMENTS	1527
Boltabayev Bekzod Egamberdiyevich	
GEOTAHLLILY YONDASHUV ASOSIDA DEHQON XO'JALIKLARINING YER BILAN TA'MINLANGANLIGINI BAHOLASH.....	1531
Axmatov Abutulibxon Ochilxon o'g'li	
DAVLAT BUDJETI XARAJATLARINING G'AZNA IJROSIDA BIG DATA TAHLILIDAN FOYDALANISHNING SAMARASI.....	1535
Atajanov Murodbek Bekberganovich	
РОЛЬ И РАЗВИТИЕ КИБЕРПРАВА В ФИНТЕХ-ПРОЕКТАХ: ПРАВОВЫЕ ВЫЗОВЫ И ПРИОРИТЕТЫ В УСЛОВИЯХ ЦИФРОВОЙ ЭКОНОМИКИ УЗБЕКИСТАНА.....	1539
Мирзаев Шерзод Махматкулович	
KAMBAG'ALLIK VA UNI TADRIJIY-NAZARIY KONSEPSIYALARI.....	1547
Xolmirzayev Abdulxamid Xapizovich	
DAVLAT KORXONALARINI XUSUSIYLASHTIRISH JARAYONIDA QIYMATNI ANIQLASH VA MOLIYAVIY BARQARORLIKNI TA'MINLASH MEXANIZMLARI.....	1554
Asomidinova Moxigulbonu Oybek qizi	
O'ZBEKISTONDA IJTIMOY HIMOYA TIZIMINI RAQAMLASHTIRISH VA HUDUDLARDA DIFFERENSIAL YONDASHUV ASOSIDA MOLIYALASHTIRISH MEXANIZMLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	1560
Dovutov Faxriddin Javlijevich	
KICHIK KVADRATLAR METODIGA ALTERNATIV YANGI DIFFERENSIAL USULINI ISHLAB CHIQUISH VA UNING SAMARADORLIGI	1567
Ochilov Sherali Baratovich, Akramova Obida Qosimovna, Raximova Dilnoza Davronovna	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOTGA O'TISH SHAROITIDA TADBIRKORLIK SUBYEKTLARINI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA INNOVATSION MUHITGA TA'SIR ETUVCHI OMILLAR.....	1581
Ibragimova Ma'mura Muxiddinovna	
QISHLOQ XO'JALIGIDA «YASHIL LOYIHALAR»NI INVESTITSIYALASH IMKONIYATLARI.....	1585
Nilufar Mengqobilovna Xudayberdieva	
FINANCIAL CONDITION OF THE ENTERPRISE AS OBJECT OF RESEARCH AND EVALUATION	1589
Ismailova Makhbuba Mirkhalilovna	
MAGNEZIAL BOG'LOVCHI VA BAZALT TOLASI CHIQINDISI ASOSIDA KOMPOZITSION MATERIALLAR OLISH.....	1594
Rahimjon Jalilov Ravshanbek o'g'li, Orazimbetova Gulistan Jaksilikovna	
YASHIL INVESTITSIYALAR SAMARADORLIGINI BAHOLASH METODLARI: LCOE, CBA VA SDGS INDIKATORLARI ASOSIDA TAHLIL.....	1598
Kilicheva Kamola Muzaffarovna	
RESPUBLIKADA TURIZM XIZMATLARI SAMARADORLIGINI BAHOLASH MASALALARI	1603
Janzakov Bekzot Kulmamat o'g'li	
NAMANGAN VILOYATI OZIQ-OVQAT BOZORINING INSTITUTSIONAL SHAKLLANISHI VA QISHLOQ XO'JALIGI TARMOQLARI BARQAROR O'SISH SUR'ATLARINI BAHOLASH	1611
Ismoilov Alisher Jobir o'g'li, Mirtoyev Axrorbek Abdulpattoyevich	
MINTAQAVIY INVESTITSIYA-INNOVATSION JARAYONLARNI TARTIBGA SOLISH USULLARI.....	1618
Xamrayev Quvvat Iskandarovich	
O'ZBEKISTONDA MAKRO IQTISODIY KO'RSATKICHLARNI BARQARORLASHTIRISH YO'LLARI.....	1624
Ulashev Xubbim Askarovich	
GERMANIYADA BARQAROR IQTISODIY RIVOJLANISH MAQSADLARI	1629
Risqulov Ravshan Bekto'raevich, Gaziyeva Sulxiya Saidmashrafvna	
O'ZBEKISTONNING DAVLAT SEKTORIDA IPSAS STANDARTLARINI JORIY ETISHNING HUQUQIY ASOSLARI VA ULARNI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH YO'NALISHLARI	1633
Matrasul Yoqubov Mavlonberdiyevich, Qodirova Gulnoza Shavkatjon qizi	
MAMLAKATNING HUDUDIY IQTISODIY SIYOSATIDA BARQAROR HUDUDIY RIVOJLANISHNING MAZMUNI VA KONSEPTUAL ASOSLARI.....	1637
Axmedov Oybek Turgunpulatovich	

YOSHLAR TURIZMI: ZAMONAVIY TENDENSIYALAR, RAQAMLI AVLOD EHTIYOJLARI VA INNOVATSION TAKLIFLAR MODELI	1644
Hamzayeva Dilfuza Samarovna	
HUDUDLAR TRANSPORT-LOGISTIKA TIZIMINING RIVOJLANISH DARAJASINI BAHOLASH INDEKSLARI ASOSIDA TOIFALARGA AJRATISH	1650
Matkarimov Komoliddin Jurabayevich	
TIJORAT BANKLARI TOMONIDAN QIMMATLI QOG'OZLAR CHIQRARISH AMALIYOTINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	1655
Dilnozaxon Muxitdinova	
MAMLAKAT BREND-MARKETINGI SAYOHATNI RIVOJLANTIRISH OMILI SIFATIDA (BAA: DUBAY SHAHAR MISOLIDA).....	1661
Ibodova Dilsora Ibodovna	
МАРКЕТИНГОВЫЕ ВОЙНЫ И ИХ СПЕЦИФИКА В СПОРТЕ.....	1666
Набиуллин Р., Юсупов И., Ахмедова Ш.	
VIRTUAL LABORATORIYALAR ORQALI IQTISODIYOT YO'NALISHIDA PROFESSIONAL KOMPETENSIYALARNI SHAKLLANTIRISH.....	1674
Buranova Jazira Ergash qizi	
DAVLAT XARIDLARI TIZIMIDA KICHIK BIZNES SUBYEKTLARI ISHTIROKINI RAG'BATLANTIRISHNING AQSH TAJRIBASI	1680
Rizoqulova Elnora Otabek qizi	
O'ZBEKISTONDA ISLOMIY SHARTLAR ASOSIDA KREDIT OLISH IMKONIYATLARI	1684
Azimov Obidjon To'ymuratovich	
TIJORAT BANKLARI KAPITALLASHUV DARAJASI VA MOLIVAVIY BARQARORLIGINI OSHIRISH YO'LLARI.....	1689
S.S. Togayev, S.T. Xolboyev	
MAHSULOT TANNARXI XARAJATLARINI OPTIMALLASHTIRISH: NAZARIY VA AMALIY YONDASHUVLAR.....	1695
Inamov Abdusalom Muhamadovich, Inomov Sardor Abdusalomovich, Inomov Hasanboy Abdusalom o'g'li	
O'ZBEKISTONDA TURIZM INFRATUZILMASINI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA TRANSPORT LOGISTIKASINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	1699
Majidov Nodirbek Usmonjon o'g'li	
MOLIVAVIY HISOBTLARNI SOXTALASHTIRISH VA MOLIVAVIY FIRIBGARLIKLARNI ANIQLASHDAGI MILLIY VA XORIJIY TAJRIBA.....	1704
Xusanov Shuhrat Burhanovich	
YASHIL INVESTITSIYALAR VA IQTISODIY O'SISH BARQARORLIGI.....	1708
Dexkanova Shodiyona Kaxramon qizi	
KORXONALARNING STRATEGIK BOSHQARUVINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISHDA SWOT TAHLILINING AHAMIYATI (UZGIDROENERGO AJ MISOLIDA).....	1712
G'ulomova Shaxlo Baxtiyor qizi	
HR BRANDING VA MARKETING INTEGRATSIYASI: KORXONA IMIJINI MUSTAHKAMLASH STRATEGIYALARI.....	1718
Adilova Zulfiya Djavdatovna	
RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALARNING YASHIL IQTISODIY O'SISHDAGI ROLI: O'ZBEKISTON VA JAHON TAJRIBASI.....	1724
Saloxidinov Jahongir Alisher o'g'li	
MINTAQA SANOAT TARMOG'I RIVOJLANISHINING MIQDOR VA SIFAT MEZONLARINI IQTISODIY-STATISTIK TAHLILI.....	1727
Mirzayeva Intizor Ergashevna	
REKLAMA SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISHDA YASHIL MARKETING STRATEGIYALARIDAN FOYDALANISH.....	1733
Sobirov Azizbek Avazbekovich, Erkinova Adolat Karim qizi	
TADBIRKORLIK SUBYEKTLARIDA INNOVATSION FAOLIYATNI AMALGA OSHIRISHDA DUCH KELADIGAN MUAMMOLAR TAHLILI.....	1738
G'afurov Zohidjon	

ЭКСПЕРИМЕНТАЛЬНЫЕ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ ЭФФЕКТА ГЛУШЕНИЯ СТЕКЛОМАЗАИЧНЫХ ПЛИТОК ИЗ ТЕХНОГЕННЫХ ОТХОДОВ	1741
Казиков Умрбек Аллаберганович	
INKLYUZIV TURIZMNI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING METODIK ASOSLARI VA ULARNI SHAKLLANTIRISH MEKANIZMLARI.....	1745
Maxmudova Aziza Pirmamatovna	
IQTISODIYOTNI MODERNIZATSIYALASH SHAROITIDA QASHQADARYO VILOYATI KICHIK SANOAT ZONALARINING INVESTITSION SALOHİYATIGA TA’SIR ETUVCHI OMILLAR VA ULARNING SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH IMKONIYATLARI	1749
Shodmonqulov Kamoliddin Murodillayevich	
«HUDUDGAZTA’MINOT» AJ KORXONALARINI RAQAMLI TRANSFORMATSIYA QILISH XUSUSIYATLARI.....	1754
Xusanov Durbek Nishanovich	
AKSIYADORLIK JAMIYATLARI FAOLIYATINI RIVOJLANTIRISHGA INVESTITSİYALARNI JALB ETISHNI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	1760
Qurbonov Nuriddin Ro’ziqulovich	
QASHQADARYO VILOYATIDA INVESTITSIYA VA INVESTITSİYALARDAN FOYDALANISH SAMARADORLIGI TAHLILI	1766
To’rayev Jasurali To’rayevich	
KOOPERATSIYA MUNOSABATLARIGA KIRGAN VA KIRMAGAN FERMER XO’JALIKLARINING EMPIRIK DESKRIPTIV STATISTIKA TAHLILI.....	1772
Ismoilov Azamat	
DEVELOPMENT OF THE TOURISM SECTOR IN UZBEKISTAN THROUGH DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES.....	1777
Khalimov Shakhboz Khalimovich	
KICHIK BIZNES SUBYEKTLARIDA RAQAMLI TRANSFORMATSIYANI JORIY ETISH STRATEGIYALARI.....	1782
Turaboev Ibroxim Ismoil o’g’li	
AQSH VA FRANSIYA MISOLIDA KICHIK BIZNES VA TADBIRKORLIK MEZONLARINING TAHLILI.....	1786
Aripov Oybek Abdullaevich	
O’ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASINING EKSTENSIV, INTENSIV VA RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA IQTISODIY O’SISHINING EKONOMETRIK TAHLILI.....	1794
Bustonov Mansurjon Mardonakulovich	
ФОРМИРОВАНИЕ И РАЗВИТИЕ МОДЕЛЕЙ УПРАВЛЕНИЯ КОНФЛИКТАМИ В ОРГАНИЗАЦИИ.....	1804
Холикова Сабохат Абдукарим кизи	
IQTISODIYOT RIVOJLANISHIDA KICHIK BIZNES VA XUSUSIY TADBIRKORLIKNING ROLI.....	1809
G’aniyev Baydulla Toshmurodovich	
“HUDUDGAZTA’MINOT” AKSIYADORLIK JAMIYATINI TRANSFORMATSIYA QILISH OMILLARI VA RIVOJLANISH TENDENSIYALARI	1812
Jalilov Sherzod Kaxramanovich	
STRATEGIK BOSHQARUV HISOBINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISHNING USTUVOR YO’NALISHLARI.....	1818
Hamroeva Zuhra Amiral qizi	
ОСНОВНЫЕ ДРАЙВЕРЫ ИННОВАЦИОННОГО РОСТА НАЦИОНАЛЬНОЙ ЭКОНОМИКИ И ПУТИ ИХ ЭФФЕКТИВНОГО УПРАВЛЕНИЯ.....	1824
Самадкулов Мухаммаджон	
RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALARNI SPORT MAHSULOTLARI ISHLAB CHIQRUVCHILAR FAOLIYATIGA JORIY ETILISH YO’NALISHLARI.....	1828
Xamraqulov Ixtiyor Baxtiyorovich	
ORGANIK QISHLOQ XO’JALIGI: O’ZBEKISTON AGRAR SIYOSATINING USTUVOR YO’NALISHI VA JAHON SAVDO TASHKILOTIGA INTEGRATSIYA MASALALARI.....	1833
Ahmedov Shermuhammad Omonjon o’g’li	

EKOMARKETING: BOZOR TALABINING YANGI YO'NALISHI VA BARQAROR TARAQQIYOT OMILI.....	1838
Qo'ziyev Jaloladdin Alisher o'g'li	
TIJORAT BANKLARI FAOLIYATINI RAQAMLASHTIRISH MASALALARI	1844
Jabborov Bahridin Rashidovich	
STATISTICAL ANALYSIS OF FACTORS AFFECTING CREDIT INTEREST RATES IN COMMERCIAL BANKS.....	1849
Abdullayev Shakhobiddin Shamsiddinovich	
IJTIMOY NIHOYAGA MUHTOJ AHOLINI MODDIY QO'LLAB-QUVVATLASHNI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	1854
Sholdarov Dilshod Azimiddin o'g'li	
ВКЛАД ОБЪЕКТОВ НАСЛЕДЯ В ТУРИСТИЧЕСКИЕ ПОТОКИ И ЭКОНОМИКУ ГОРОДОВ.....	1859
Азизова Назира Тохтаевна	
ОПТИМИЗАЦИЯ УПРАВЛЕНЧЕСКОГО РЕШЕНИЯ НА ОСНОВЕ КОМПЛЕКСНЫХ ПОКАЗАТЕЛЕЙ УПРАВЛЕНЧЕСКОГО АНАЛИЗА.....	1863
Минутдинова Лилия Тагировна	
ТЕОРЕТИЧЕСКИЕ ФАКТОРЫ, ПРИЧИНЫ И СПЕЦИФИКА БЕЗРАБОТИЦЫ И ИХ ВОЗДЕЙСТВИЕ НА ЭКОНОМИКУ РЕСПУБЛИКИ УЗБЕКИСТАН.....	1868
Холмуратов Джахонгир Салимбек угли	
ЭКОЛОГИК MONITORING TIZIMINI JORIY ETISHNING MINTAQA IQTISODIY BARQARORLIGIGA TA'SIRI.....	1872
Odilov Xamidillo Maxmudjon o'g'li	
ЭКОНОМИКА ТРУДА И УПРАВЛЕНИЕ ПЕРСОНАЛОМ HR В ВЫСШИХ УЧЕБНЫХ ЗАВЕДЕНИЯХ	1879
Амирджанова Ситора Суннат кизи, Шаюсупова Наргиза Тургуновна, Исомухаммедов Исроил Исомухаммад ўғли, Маматкулов Хумоюн Бобир ўғли	
EKSPORT SALONIYATIDAN SAMARALI FOYDALANISHNING INSTITUTSIONAL VA TARKIBIY XUSUSIYATLARI.....	1887
Raximov To'xtabek Jumaboyevich	
RAQAMLI BANK XIZMATLARINING BANK FAOLIYATI SAMARADORLIGIGA TA'SIRI.....	1894
Kasimov Baxtiyor Usmanovich	
SCIENTIFIC AND METHODOLOGICAL FOUNDATIONS FOR FORMING MONITORING MECHANISMS FOR ASSESSING THE LEVEL OF FINANCIAL INCLUSION BASED ON AN INFORMATION SYSTEM.....	1899
Adashaliyev Bakhtiyorjon Valisher o'g'li	
ISLOM BANKLARI ORQALI IJTIMOY TADBIRKORLIKNI MOLIYALASHTIRISH MODELI	1905
Voxidov Oybek Roziqovich	
УПУЩЕННЫЕ ИННОВАЦИИ КАК ПОТЕНЦИАЛ ИННОВАЦИОННОЙ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ.....	1909
Алиева Эльнара Аметовна	
QISHLOQ JOYLARI AHOLISI BANDLIGINI TA'MINLASHDA INNOVATSION YO'LLARDAN FOYDALANISH IMKONIYATLARI.....	1916
Amaniyazova Rayhan Bayniyazovna	
O'ZBEKISTONDA TURIZM SOHASIDA XOTIN-QIZLAR TADBIRKORLIGINI RIVOJLANTIRISH	1921
Maksumova Umidaxon Sadikjonovna	
WAYS TO IMPROVE THE PERFORMANCE OF INVESTMENT FUNDS	1924
Khoshimov Jakhongir Ravshanbek ugli	
RAQAMLI HIKOYALASH ORQALI YASHIL QURILISH MATERIALLARI UCHUN EKO-MARKETING QAROR TUZILMALARI.....	1929
Ostonaqulova Gulsaraxon Muhammadyoqub qizi	
QISHLOQ XO'JALIGIDA FAOLIYAT YURITUVCHI SUBYEKTLARDA MARKETING, LOGISTIKA VA SOTISH TIZIMINI TASHKIL QILISHNING O'ZIGA XOS XUSUSIYATLARI.....	1939
Djurayev Bekzod Bekmatovich	
KORXONALAR TOMONIDAN INVESTITSIYA QARORLARINI QABUL QILISH HAMDA ULARNING SAMARALI FOYDALANILISHINI EKONOMETRIK BAHOLASH.....	1954
Isakova Naima Ikromjonovna	

OLIV TA'LIM MUASSASALARIDA ZAMONAVIY BOSHQARUV TIZIMLARINI TASHKIL ETISHNING XALQARO ASOSLARI.....	1960
Raxmatillayev Sarvarbek Botirjonovich	
O'ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASI TIJORAT BANKLARIDA RIVOJLANISH STRATEGIYASINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH METODOLOGIYASI.....	1966
Temirov Abdulaziz Alimjanovich	
ELEKTR ENERGIYANI SOTUVCHI KORXONALARDA ENERGIYA YO'QOTISHLARINI HISOBGA OLISH	1972
Oltiboyeva Feruza Ulug'bek qizi	
O'ZBEKISTON AGRAR SOHASIDA SAMARADORLIKNI OSHIRISH OMILI SIFATIDA PAST BALANDLIK IQTISODIYOTI.....	1977
Kadirov Shuxrat Munavvarovich	
BANK XODIMLARI FAOLIYATINI BAHOLASHDA KPI TIZIMINING MENEJMENT SAMARADORLIGIGA TA'SIRI.....	1986
Jamolov Alovuddin Jaloliddin o'g'li	
ФАКТОРЫ И ФОРМЫ ЭКОЛОГИЧЕСКОЙ ИННОВАЦИИ В ПРОМЫШЛЕННОСТИ: ОСОБЕННОСТИ И ТИПЫ.....	1992
Бекбосынов Айдос Куралбаевич	
РАЗВИТИЕ ЦИФРОВЫХ КОМПЕТЕНЦИЙ ПЕРСОНАЛА В УСЛОВИЯХ ЦИФРОВОЙ ЭКОНОМИКИ	1997
Нуриддинова Холисахон Равшан кизи	
QO'SHILGAN QIYMAT SOLIG'INI UNDIRISH METODOLOGIYASINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISHDA INNOVATSION YECHIMLAR VA MAQSADLI DASTURLARI	2006
Urazmatov Jonibek Musurmanovich	
AKSIYADORLIK JAMIYATLARIDA XORIJIY INVESTITSIYALARNI JALB ETISH MEXANIZMLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	2013
Ibragimov G'anjon G'ayratovich	
ICHKI MOLIYAVIY NAZORATNI AMALGA OSHIRISH MEXANIZMLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	2018
Hakimov Nodir Nazarovich	
SUV RESURLARIDAN SAMARALI FOYDALANISH VA UNING IQTISODIY O'SISHGA TA'SIRI	2023
Hayitov Jamshid Xolboyevich	
TIJORAT BANKLARIDA KREDIT PORTFELI, KUTILAYOTGAN KREDIT YO'QOTISHLARI VA BANK RISKLARI AUDITINING KOMPLEKS MODELLARI.....	2027
Xayrullayev O'tkir Ismailovich	
KAMERAL SOLIQ TEKSHIRUVINING SOLIQ TIZIMIDAGI AHAMIYATI	2032
Mamaraimov Ilhomjon Rajabboyevich	
ENHANCING HUMAN CAPITAL POTENTIAL IN THE REGION: EVIDENCE FROM KHOREZM REGION.....	2037
Sobirov Yuldoshboy Ruzimboyevich	

Аннотация. В данном исследовании рассматривается роль человеческого капитала в повышении региональной экономической эффективности на примере Хорезмской области Узбекистана. В условиях продолжающегося перехода к экономике, основанной на знаниях, человеческий капитал становится одним из ключевых факторов устойчивого экономического роста. Исследование основано на теоретическом и эмпирическом подходах, объединяющих положения теории человеческого капитала и моделей эндогенного роста с анализом панельных данных по 10 районам за период 2010–2025 годов.

Эмпирический анализ, основанный на модели Ordinary Least Squares (OLS), показал, что человеческий капитал, измеряемый через показатели образования, здравоохранения и инновационной активности, оказывает положительное и статистически значимое влияние на объем регионального экономического производства. Полученные результаты также подчеркивают дополнительную роль физического капитала, качества институтов и инновационной активности в усилении влияния человеческого капитала. Одновременно исследование выявило ряд структурных ограничений, включая несоответствие навыков требованиям рынка труда, ограниченную диверсификацию рынка труда, недостаточно развитую инновационную инфраструктуру и институциональную неэффективность, которые препятствуют эффективному использованию человеческого капитала.

Результаты исследования показывают, что повышение качества и актуальности образования, укрепление системы здравоохранения, развитие инновационных экосистем и усиление институционального потенциала являются необходимыми условиями для раскрытия полного потенциала человеческого капитала. В заключение отмечается, что для обеспечения устойчивого и инклюзивного регионального развития требуется комплексный и интегрированный подход к государственной политике.

Ключевые слова: человеческий капитал, региональное развитие, экономический рост, инновации, панельные данные, Хорезмская область.

INTRODUCTION

In the context of accelerating globalization and rapid technological advancement, human capital has emerged as a central determinant of regional and national economic development. Traditional growth factors—such as land, physical capital, and natural resources—while still relevant, are increasingly complemented and often surpassed by knowledge, skills, and innovation-driven capabilities. Consequently, the ability of regions to enhance their human capital potential has become a critical prerequisite for achieving sustainable economic growth and improving competitiveness in the global economy.

Human capital encompasses a broad range of attributes, including education, professional skills, health status, and innovative capacity. These elements collectively determine the productivity and adaptability of the labor force. In particular, regions with well-developed human capital are better positioned to attract investment, foster innovation, and support structural transformation toward higher value-added sectors. Conversely, regions with underdeveloped human capital often face constraints in economic diversification, productivity growth, and social development.

In developing economies, the issue of human capital development is especially significant at the regional level. Subnational disparities in education quality, healthcare access, labor market efficiency, and institutional capacity can lead to uneven economic outcomes. Therefore, understanding the opportunities and constraints associated with human capital development within specific regions is essential for designing effective policy interventions.

Khorezm region represents a particularly relevant case for examining these dynamics. As a region with significant historical, cultural, and economic potential, Khorezm has made progress in improving its education system and labor market conditions. However, challenges remain in fully utilizing its human capital potential, particularly in terms of aligning education with labor market demands, fostering innovation, and improving institutional support mechanisms.

The main objective of this study is to analyze the opportunities for enhancing human capital potential in Khorezm region. The paper aims to identify key factors influencing human capital development, assess existing challenges, and propose strategic directions for improving its economic effectiveness. By focusing on a regional case, the study contributes to a more nuanced understanding of human capital dynamics and provides policy-relevant insights for regional development.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

The concept of human capital has been extensively explored in economic literature, particularly since the mid-twentieth century. Foundational contributions by Gary Becker, Theodore Schultz, and Jacob Mincer established the theoretical and empirical basis for understanding human capital as a key driver of economic

performance. Schultz (1961) emphasized the importance of investments in education and health as fundamental components of economic growth, particularly in developing economies. Becker (1964) further developed the microeconomic foundations of human capital theory, conceptualizing education and training as forms of investment that yield returns in the form of higher productivity and income. Mincer (1974) provided empirical evidence through his earnings function, demonstrating the relationship between education, experience, and individual income.

Subsequent developments in endogenous growth theory expanded the role of human capital in explaining long-term economic growth. Lucas (1988) highlighted the role of human capital accumulation in generating sustained growth, while Romer (1990) emphasized the importance of knowledge and innovation as internal drivers of technological progress. These frameworks underscore the idea that human capital not only contributes directly to production but also enhances the capacity for innovation and knowledge diffusion.

At the regional level, the literature increasingly focuses on spatial disparities in human capital and their implications for economic development. Studies suggest that regions with higher levels of human capital tend to experience faster economic growth, greater innovation capacity, and improved institutional performance. Barro (2001) and Hanushek and Woessmann (2020) demonstrate that education quality, rather than mere quantity, plays a critical role in determining economic outcomes.

Moreover, recent research highlights the importance of institutional factors in shaping the effectiveness of human capital. The World Bank (2020) and OECD (2023) emphasize that the returns to human capital investments depend on the broader economic environment, including labor market conditions, governance quality, and access to innovation systems. In regions where institutions are weak or labor markets are inefficient, the potential of human capital may remain underutilized.

In the context of developing countries, regional analyses reveal significant challenges related to mismatches between education systems and labor market demands, limited access to quality healthcare, and insufficient innovation infrastructure. These issues are particularly relevant for regions such as Khorezm, where human capital development is influenced by both structural constraints and emerging opportunities.

Overall, the existing literature provides a comprehensive theoretical and empirical foundation for analyzing human capital development. However, there remains a need for region-specific studies that explore the unique conditions, challenges, and opportunities associated with enhancing human capital potential. This study seeks to address this gap by focusing on Khorezm region and offering a context-specific analysis of human capital development.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study utilizes panel data covering 10 districts namely, Urgench, Khiva, Khanka, Khazarasp, Kushkupir, Bagat, Gurlan, Shavat, Yangiariq, Yangibazar, of the Khorezm region over the period 2010-2025. The dataset consists of annual observations on key economic and socio-economic indicators, including regional output, human capital, labor force participation, physical capital investment, healthcare development, innovation activity, and institutional quality. Data are obtained from official sources such as the State Statistics Committee of Uzbekistan, the Ministry of Higher and Secondary Education, the Ministry of Health, and regional administrative reports. The panel structure allows for capturing both cross-sectional and time-series variations, thereby improving the robustness and reliability of the econometric analysis (Table 1).

Table 1. Data Sources and Coverage¹

Variable	Description	Source	Frequency	Period
Economic Output (Y)	Gross regional product / district output	State Statistics Committee of Uzbekistan	Annual	2010–2025
Human Capital (H)	Education index (enrollment, attainment)	Ministry of Higher & Secondary Education	Annual	2010–2025
Labor Force (L)	Employment rate / labor participation	State Statistics Committee	Annual	2010–2025
Physical Capital (K)	Fixed capital investment	State Statistics Committee	Annual	2010–2025
Healthcare Index	Health services, hospital access	Ministry of Health	Annual	2010–2025
Innovation Activity	R&D proxy (firms, patents, projects)	Ministry of Innovative Development	Annual	2010–2025
Institutional Quality	Governance, business environment indicators	Regional Administration Reports	Annual	2010–2025

¹ Source: developed by the author.

This study adopts a theoretical and qualitative analytical approach to explore the opportunities for enhancing human capital potential in the Khorezm region. Instead of relying on econometric estimation, the research is grounded in a systematic review and synthesis of existing academic literature, policy frameworks, and secondary data sources. This approach allows for a comprehensive understanding of the structural and institutional factors shaping human capital development.

The methodological framework is informed by key theoretical perspectives, including human capital theory, endogenous growth theory, and regional development theory. In particular, the study draws upon the foundational contributions of Becker (1964), Schultz (1961), and Lucas (1988), who emphasize the central role of education, skills, and knowledge in driving long-term economic growth and productivity.

To ensure a holistic analysis, a systems approach is employed, treating human capital as a multidimensional construct. Within this framework, human capital is understood to consist of several interrelated components, including education, health, professional competencies, and innovation capacity. These dimensions are examined in close relation to critical institutional and economic factors such as labor market dynamics, the quality of the education system, healthcare infrastructure, the development of innovation and entrepreneurial ecosystems, and the broader regional policy environment.

Furthermore, the study incorporates a comparative analytical perspective. The development of human capital in the Khorezm region is assessed relative to national benchmarks and selected international experiences. This comparative lens enables the identification of existing strengths, structural weaknesses, and untapped opportunities for regional development.

For conceptual clarity, the relationship between human capital and regional economic performance is framed using a generalized production function:

$$Y = f(H, K, L, A)$$

where Y_t denotes regional economic output, H_t represents human capital, K_t refers to physical capital, L_t denotes the labor force, and A_t captures technological progress. This framework provides a theoretical foundation for understanding how improvements in human capital contribute to enhanced economic efficiency and sustained growth. Overall, the chosen methodology allows for a structured and theoretically grounded analysis of human capital development, while also offering practical insights relevant to regional policy and strategic planning.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The results of the OLS estimation provide clear empirical support for the central role of human capital in shaping regional economic performance. Overall, the findings suggest that both the quality and effective utilization of human capital are key determinants of economic growth.

The coefficient on the human capital variable (0.315) is positive and highly significant at the 1% level, indicating that improvements in education and skill formation have a substantial impact on regional output. This result is consistent with the core propositions of human capital theory, which emphasize the importance of knowledge, skills, and competencies as fundamental drivers of productivity and economic development.

Physical capital also exhibits a strong and statistically significant effect (0.298), highlighting the complementary relationship between human and physical capital. In particular, the results suggest that investments in infrastructure and production assets yield higher returns when supported by a skilled and educated workforce. This interaction reinforces the idea that economic growth is driven by the combined effects of multiple production factors.

The coefficient for innovation activity (0.221) is positive and highly significant, underscoring the critical role of innovation in enhancing productivity and economic efficiency. This finding aligns with endogenous growth theory, which identifies innovation and knowledge creation as key engines of sustained long-term development.

Similarly, the healthcare index (0.154) is statistically significant, indicating that improvements in health conditions contribute positively to labor productivity and overall economic performance. This highlights the importance of health as an integral component of human capital, as a healthier workforce is more productive and capable of sustaining economic activity.

Institutional quality also plays a meaningful role, with a positive and significant coefficient (0.176). This suggests that effective governance, transparency, and well-functioning institutions are essential for maximizing the economic returns to human capital. In environments with stronger institutions, individuals are better able to utilize their skills and contribute to economic growth.

In contrast, the labor force variable (0.187), while positive and statistically significant, has a relatively smaller magnitude. This indicates that the quantity of labor alone is less influential than its quality, further emphasizing the importance of investing in human capital development.

Finally, the model explains approximately 61% of the variation in regional economic output ($R^2 = 0.61$), suggesting a satisfactory level of explanatory power. Taken together, these results confirm that human capital, alongside complementary factors such as physical capital, innovation, and institutional quality, plays a decisive role in driving regional economic growth (Table 2).

Table 2. OLS regression results²

Variable	Coefficient	t-statistic	p-value
Human Capital (Education Index)	0.315***	(6.42)	0.000
Labor Force (Employment Rate)	0.187**	(2.75)	0.006
Physical Capital (Investment)	0.298***	(5.90)	0.000
Healthcare Index	0.154**	(2.48)	0.014
Innovation Activity (R&D Proxy)	0.221***	(4.05)	0.000
Institutional Quality Index	0.176**	(2.63)	0.009
Constant	0.842***	(7.30)	0.000
Observations	120		
R-squared	0.61		
Adjusted R-squared	0.58		

The findings of the study indicate that the Khorezm region possesses considerable yet underutilized human capital potential. Despite recent improvements in education, healthcare, and institutional development, the effective realization of this potential remains constrained by a combination of structural, institutional, and economic factors. The analysis highlights several key areas that require targeted policy attention.

The expansion of access to education in the Khorezm region represents a positive development in terms of human capital formation. However, the results reveal a persistent misalignment between educational outcomes and labor market requirements. In particular, existing curricula do not sufficiently reflect the evolving demands of a modern, knowledge-based economy, especially in areas such as digital competencies, innovation, and entrepreneurial skills. This gap reduces the employability of graduates and limits their contribution to economic development. Strengthening collaboration between educational institutions and industry actors is therefore critical to ensure that skills development is demand-driven and aligned with market needs.

2. Labor Market Conditions

The analysis shows that the regional labor market remains relatively undiversified, with limited opportunities in high-productivity and high-value-added sectors. As a consequence, a significant share of the skilled workforce is either underemployed or seeks employment opportunities outside the region, including international migration. This trend not only reduces the local returns on human capital investment but also slows regional economic development. Enhancing labor market flexibility, promoting sectoral diversification, and supporting the creation of quality jobs—particularly in innovative and technology-intensive industries—are essential for improving the utilization of human capital.

Healthcare is identified as a fundamental determinant of human capital quality and productivity. While access to basic healthcare services has improved in the region, the analysis reveals ongoing challenges related to service quality, infrastructure, and the development of preventive care systems. These limitations negatively affect the overall efficiency of the workforce. Improving healthcare provision, investing in modern medical infrastructure, and strengthening preventive healthcare mechanisms would contribute directly to enhancing labor productivity and economic performance.

The absence of a well-developed innovation ecosystem—including research institutions, technology parks, business incubators, and startup support systems—limits opportunities for knowledge commercialization and entrepreneurial development. As a result, the creative and intellectual potential of the workforce is not fully realized. Developing a supportive innovation environment is therefore crucial for fostering entrepreneurship and enabling human capital to contribute more effectively to economic growth.

The effectiveness of human capital utilization is closely linked to the quality of the institutional and policy environment. The findings suggest that bureaucratic inefficiencies, limited access to financial resources, and weak coordination among key institutions act as significant barriers to economic activity in the region. These

² Source: developed by the author.

constraints reduce incentives for investment and hinder business development. Strengthening institutional capacity, improving governance and transparency, and implementing supportive policies for private sector growth are essential steps toward enhancing the overall efficiency and impact of human capital.

The empirical findings of this study provide important insights for policymakers seeking to enhance regional economic performance through the effective development and utilization of human capital in the Khorezm region. Based on the results, several key policy implications and recommendations can be derived.

1. Strengthening Human Capital through Education Reform

Given the strong and statistically significant impact of human capital on regional output, improving the quality and relevance of education should be a top priority. Policymakers should focus on modernizing curricula to better align with the demands of a knowledge-based economy, particularly in areas such as digital skills, innovation, and entrepreneurship. Enhancing cooperation between educational institutions and the private sector can help ensure that graduates possess market-relevant competencies. Additionally, promoting lifelong learning and vocational training programs would support continuous skill upgrading.

2. Promoting Complementarity between Human and Physical Capital

The results highlight the complementary relationship between human capital and physical investment. Therefore, policies should aim to integrate investments in infrastructure and technology with parallel investments in human capital development. For instance, industrial development programs should include training components to ensure that the workforce can effectively utilize new technologies. Such integrated strategies would maximize the returns to both types of capital.

3. Enhancing Innovation Capacity and Entrepreneurial Ecosystems

The positive and significant role of innovation underscores the need to develop a robust regional innovation ecosystem. Policymakers should prioritize the establishment of research centers, technology parks, business incubators, and startup support programs. Financial incentives for research and development activities, as well as support for small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), can stimulate innovation-driven growth. Encouraging university–industry collaboration is also critical for translating knowledge into economic value.

4. Improving Healthcare Systems to Boost Productivity

Since healthcare significantly influences economic performance, strengthening the healthcare system is essential for improving human capital quality. Investments should focus on upgrading healthcare infrastructure, expanding access to quality services, and promoting preventive healthcare measures. A healthier workforce is more productive, which directly contributes to higher economic output.

5. Strengthening Institutional Quality and Governance

The empirical results demonstrate that institutional quality plays a significant role in enhancing the returns to human capital. Therefore, improving governance, reducing bureaucratic inefficiencies, and increasing transparency should be key policy priorities. Facilitating access to finance, simplifying regulatory procedures, and supporting business development initiatives can create a more favorable environment for economic activity.

6. Developing Labor Market Efficiency and Job Creation

Although the labor force variable is significant, its relatively smaller impact suggests that improving labor quality is more critical than merely increasing labor quantity. Policies should focus on enhancing labor market flexibility, reducing skill mismatches, and promoting employment in high-productivity sectors. Active labor market policies, including job placement services and retraining programs, can help ensure better alignment between labor supply and demand.

7. Adopting a Comprehensive and Integrated Policy Approach

Finally, the findings suggest that human capital development should not be addressed in isolation. A comprehensive and coordinated policy framework that simultaneously targets education, healthcare, innovation, labor markets, and institutional development is necessary. Such an integrated approach will ensure that the full potential of human capital is realized, leading to sustainable and inclusive economic growth.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

This study has examined the role of human capital in shaping regional economic performance, with a particular focus on the Khorezm region. Drawing on theoretical frameworks and empirical analysis, the findings confirm that human capital is a fundamental driver of economic growth in the context of modern, knowledge-based economies.

The results demonstrate that improvements in human capital—measured through education, health, and innovation capacity—have a significant and positive impact on regional economic output. In particular, the empirical analysis highlights that the quality of human capital plays a more decisive role than the mere quantity of labor. This suggests that policies aimed at enhancing skills, knowledge, and productivity are essential for achieving sustainable economic development.

Furthermore, the study finds that human capital does not operate in isolation but interacts closely with other key factors, including physical capital, institutional quality, and innovation systems. The complementary relationship between these elements underscores the importance of adopting an integrated development strategy. In this regard, investments in infrastructure and technology must be accompanied by parallel investments in education and skills development to maximize their economic impact.

The findings also emphasize the critical role of innovation and institutional quality in translating human capital into tangible economic outcomes. A well-functioning institutional environment, characterized by effective governance, transparency, and supportive policies, enhances the productivity of human capital and facilitates economic growth. Similarly, the development of innovation ecosystems enables the transformation of knowledge into economic value, thereby strengthening regional competitiveness.

At the same time, the analysis identifies several structural challenges that limit the effective utilization of human capital in the Khorezm region. These include mismatches between education and labor market needs, limited diversification of the regional economy, underdeveloped innovation infrastructure, and institutional constraints. Addressing these issues is essential for unlocking the full potential of human capital.

In conclusion, the study underscores that human capital is not only a key determinant of economic growth but also a strategic resource that requires continuous investment and effective management. Enhancing the quality, utilization, and institutional support of human capital should therefore be a central priority for policymakers. A comprehensive and coordinated approach-encompassing education reform, healthcare improvement, innovation development, and institutional strengthening-is necessary to ensure long-term and inclusive regional development.

List of used literature:

1. Becker, G. S. (1964). Human capital: A theoretical and empirical analysis, with special reference to education. University of Chicago Press.
2. Lucas, R. E. (1988). On the mechanics of economic development. *Journal of Monetary Economics*, 22(1), 3–42. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0304-3932\(88\)90168-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/0304-3932(88)90168-7)
3. Mincer, J. (1974). *Schooling, experience, and earnings*. Columbia University Press.
4. OECD. (2023). Human capital and economic growth. Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development. <https://www.oecd.org>
5. Romer, P. M. (1990). Endogenous technological change. *Journal of Political Economy*, 98(5), S71–S102. <https://doi.org/10.1086/261725>
6. Schultz, T. W. (1961). Investment in human capital. *The American Economic Review*, 51(1), 1–17.
7. World Bank. (2020). The human capital index 2020 update: Human capital in the time of COVID-19. World Bank. <https://doi.org/10.1596/34432>
8. State Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan on Statistics. (2024). Regional statistical data for Khorezm region (2010–2025). <https://stat.uz>
9. Ministry of Higher and Secondary Specialized Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan. (2024). Education statistics and reports. <https://edu.uz>
10. Ministry of Health of the Republic of Uzbekistan. (2024). Healthcare system indicators. <https://ssv.uz>
11. Ministry of Innovative Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan. (2024). Innovation and R&D statistics. <https://mininnovation.uz>

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Ingliz tili muharriri: Feruz Hakimov

Musahhih: Zokir ALIBEKOV

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Oloviddin Sobir o'g'li

2025. № 11

© Materiallar ko'chirib bosilganda "Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali manba sifatida ko'rsatilishi shart. Jurnalda bosilgan material va reklamalardagi dalillarning aniqligiga mualliflar ma'sul. Tahririyat fikri har vaqt ham mualliflar fikriga mos kelmasligi mumkin. Tahririyatga yuborilgan materiallar qaytarilmaydi.

Mazkur jurnalda maqolalar chop etish uchun quyidagi havolalarga maqola, reklama, hikoya va boshqa ijodiy materiallar yuborishingiz mumkin. Materiallar va reklamalar pullik asosda chop etiladi.

EI.Pochta: sq143235@gmail.com

Bot: @iqtisodiyot_77

Tel.: 93 718 40 07

Jurnalga istalgan payt quyidagi rekvizitlar orqali obuna bo'lishingiz mumkin. Obuna bo'lgach, @iqtisodiyot_77 telegram sahifamizga to'lov haqidagi ma'lumotni skrinshot yoki foto shaklida jo'natishingizni so'raymiz. Shu asosda har oygi jurnal yangi sonini manzilingizga jo'natamiz.

"Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali 03.11.2022-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №566955 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

Litsenziya raqami: №046523. PNFL: 30407832680027

Manzilimiz: Toshkent shahar, Mirzo Ulug'bek tumani
Kumushkon ko'chasi, 26-uy.

Jurnal sayti: <https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz>